

Tutorial for using hydroPSO to calibrate the SWAT+ model

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1 A bit of history

When development of `hydroPSO` (Zambrano-Bigiarini & Rojas, 2013) began in 2010, R was not yet a common environment for end-to-end hydrological model calibration. To the best of our knowledge, `topmodel` was then the only hydrological model fully implemented as an R function and available from CRAN. Many operational and research workflows still relied on external model executables, configuration files, and command-line calls. For this reason, the early development of `hydroPSO` focused on providing a flexible optimisation interface for hydrological and environmental models that run as external executables on different operating systems (GNU/Linux, Windows, and macOS), while also allowing the optimisation of native R functions through a global, population-based strategy rather than a local search such as the one usually provided by `optim`.

Since then, R has continued to gain visibility in hydrology because it supports reproducible workflows, transparent data processing, model evaluation, and publication-ready graphics in a single programming environment. Several hydrological models are now available as R packages or R-callable routines, including `TUWmodel`, `airGR`, and `VIC5`. At the same time, many widely used community models, including `SWAT+`, remain distributed as external executables. This makes it increasingly useful to have a calibration tool that can interact both with external executable models and with models implemented directly in R.

This tutorial shows how to use `hydroPSO >= 0.5-0` to calibrate the semi-distributed `SWAT+` hydrological model using a ready-to-run external model setup. The example is intentionally compact, but it illustrates a workflow that hydrologists can adapt to their own catchments, forcing datasets, objective functions, and model structures. Beyond reproducing the Trancura River Basin application, the tutorial is intended to demonstrate how `hydroPSO` can support transparent, reusable, and extensible calibration experiments within the R ecosystem.

2 Citation

This tutorial is based on the vignette showing how to use `hydroPSO to calibrate TUWmodel`, with modifications mainly related to the description of the hydrological model and its parameters, as well as to the specific way in which `SWAT+` handles input time series and model outputs. If you find this vignette useful, please cite it as:

Zambrano-Bigiarini, Mauricio and Marinao, Rodrigo (2026). Tutorial for using `hydroPSO` to calibrate the `SWAT+` hydrological model. doi:10.5281/zenodo.20482309. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20482309>.

3 Required `hydroPSO` version

This tutorial was developed for `hydroPSO >= 0.5-0`, released in Github (not in CRAN) in March 2020. Although `hydroPSO` has always been able to optimise generic R functions, earlier versions were primarily designed for models executed through external files and command-line calls. Consequently, versions lower than `0.5-0` keep track of goodness-of-fit values but do not retain model simulations when calibrating an R-based model. Since `v0.5-0`, `hydroPSO` provides full support for R-based hydrological and environmental models, including the storage and post-processing of simulated time series. The same version is used here to keep a consistent, modern workflow for calibrating the external `SWAT+` executable through `hydromod()`.

4 Objective

The main objective of this tutorial is to show how to use `hydroPSO` to obtain an **acceptable** *best parameter set* for the `SWAT+` hydrological model. The emphasis is to be practical and reproducible: the document focuses on preparing input data, defining parameter bounds, configuring the external-model interface, running the optimisation, and interpreting the main calibration outputs produced by `hydroPSO`. It is not intended to provide a full theoretical treatment of calibration, verification, sensitivity analysis, or uncertainty analysis¹.

¹Some basic references are provided throughout the text to guide readers who are new to these topics.

The tutorial deliberately keeps the hydrological interpretation concise. The figures generated throughout the workflow are provided as diagnostic outputs that readers can use to examine model behaviour, parameter sensitivity, residual structure, and predictive uncertainty. This design allows hydrologists to focus on how the software components interact, and then transfer the workflow to their own modelling questions.

5 hydroPSO

`hydroPSO` is a multi-platform and model-independent R package based on Particle Swarm Optimisation [PSO; Kennedy & Eberhart (1995)]. It was designed to support three common tasks in hydrological and environmental modelling: *i*) automatic model calibration; *ii*) sensitivity analysis; and *iii*) assessment and visualisation of calibration results. The package can be coupled with models that use PEST-like template and instruction files, external executables, or native R functions. It also supports parallel execution, which is particularly relevant when the calibrated model is computationally expensive or when large parameter ensembles are required.

PSO is a population-based stochastic optimisation technique that explores a bounded parameter space through a *swarm* of candidate solutions, called particles. Each particle represents a possible parameter set and is evaluated with a user-defined objective function, such as the Kling-Gupta efficiency, Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency, root mean squared error, or any other metric appropriate for the modelling objective. During the search, particles update their position and velocity by combining information from their own best-known location and the best-known location in their neighbourhood. This mechanism allows the algorithm to balance exploration of poorly sampled regions of the parameter space with exploitation of promising parameter combinations.

For hydrological applications, this behaviour is useful because objective-function surfaces are often non-linear, multi-modal, and affected by equifinality. `hydroPSO` does not remove these modelling challenges, but it provides a structured and reproducible way to explore them, document the calibration settings, store model outputs, and analyse behavioural parameter sets. For a detailed description of the package and its hydrological applications, please refer to Zambrano-Bigiarini & Rojas (2013) and Zambrano-Bigiarini et al. (2013).

6 The basic workflow for an R-external model

The calibration of an **R-external model** with `hydroPSO` has a file-based workflow, which is illustrated by the figure shown below:

1. `ParamRanges.txt`: defines the parameters to be optimised, their search ranges and the type of modification (**TypeChange**) made for each parameter (replacement, additive or multiplicative). Its path is passed to `hydroPSO` through the `model.FUN.args` argument. The format of `ParamRanges.txt` is as follows:

Nmbr	ParameterName	MinValue	MaxValue	TypeChange	Min4Change	Max4Change
1	par1	min1	max1	repl	0	0
2	par2	min2	max2	repl	0	0
3	par3	min3	max3	repl	0	0
4	par4	min4	max4	repl	0	0
5	par5	min5	max5	repl	0	0
.
.
.
N	parN	minN	maxN	.	0	0

where `MinValue` and `MaxValue` are the minimum and maximum parameter values, respectively.

Note that care must be taken in numbering and naming the parameters to be calibrated as they require to be consistent in both files.

Using hydroPSO with R-external models

One reproducible workflow for calibration, verification and uncertainty analysis.

hydroPSO
Efficient calibration. Deeper insight.

Figure 1: Workflow for calibrating R-external environmental models with hydroPSO

2. `ParamFiles.txt` tells hydroPSO where and how each parameter is written in the external model input files, as well as the reference value (**RefValue**) to be used when the type of change is additive or multiplicative. Its path is passed to hydroPSO through the `model.FUN.args` argument. The format of `ParamFiles.txt` is as follows:

Nmbr	ParameterName	Filename	Row.Number	Col.Start	Col.End	DecimalPlaces	RefValue
1	par1	file1	x1	y1	z1	w1	rv1
2	par2	file1	x2	y2	z2	w2	rv2
3	par3	file2	x3	y3	z3	w3	rv3
4	par4	file3	x4	y4	z4	w4	rv4
1	par1	file4	x5	y5	z5	w5	rv5
1	par1	file5	x5	y5	z5	w5	rv6
.
.
.
N	parN	fileM	xN	yN	zN	wN	rvN

where:

- `ParameterNmbr` is a consecutive number assigned to each parameter,
- `ParameterName` is a user-defined parameter name,
- `Filename` is the name of the model input file (without path) where the corresponding `ParameterName` is located,
- `Row.Number` is the row number in the `Filename` file where `ParameterName` can be found,
- `Col.Start` and `Col.End` define the column numbers in the `Filename` file where `ParameterName` has to be written,
- `DecimalPlaces` defines the number of decimal places used for writing the corresponding `ParameterName` value.

Please note that the same file (file1) can include more than one model parameter (par1 and par2) located in different places in the file, and also that the same model parameter (par1) can appear in different input files (file1, file4, file5).

In addition, it is very important to define `Col.Start` and `Col.End` in such a way that the parameter value AND its decimal places fit the width defined as `Col.Start - Col.End + 1`.

For users familiar with PEST (Doherty, 2010), `Col.Start` and `Col.End` are equivalent to the token used to define where to write parameters during the optimisation.

3. **R wrapper function:** this is a user-defined function that:

- takes a parameter set (`param.values`) as first mandatory parameter
- runs the R-external model using the `hydromod` function, `ParamRanges.txt` and `ParamRanges.txt` files, and the parameter set provided by the PSO engine, and deliver model outputs
- uses `out.FUN()` argument, within the `hydromod` function, to read the model output files and returns the simulated values.
- reads observations (`obs`)
- uses `gof.FUN()` argument, within the `hydromod` function, to compare simulations with observations and returns the objective-function value (i.e., the model's performance).

2. **hydroPSO engine:** this is the main function of the `hydroPSO` package, which updates the parameter sets throughout the iterations. This function:

- takes as first argument `fn="hydromod"`, which tells `hydroPSO` that we are going to optimise an **R-external** model (and not an external model),
- takes the R wrapper function defined in the previous step (`model.FUN` and `model.FUN.args`),
- takes a parameter set (`par`), coming either from the initialisation method defined by the `Xini.type` argument during the first iteration or from the PSO engine during all subsequent iterations,
- takes the `lower` and `upper` bounds of the parameter space,
- takes the user-defined method for changing the model parameters, by default `change.type="repl"`,
- takes the user-defined PSO engine (by default, `method="SPSO-2011"`),
- provides several optional ways to customise the `hydroPSO` behaviour and the delivery of model outputs,
- uses the `hydromodInR()` function to pass the parameter set to the user-defined R wrapper function, run the model, compute model simulations, and evaluate model performance.

3. Computation of **model performance** (aka **GoF**, short for goodness-of-fit metric). The computation of model performance is carried out within the R wrapper function, using either a user-defined metric or any of the several GoFs available in the `hydroGOF` R package.

4. Several **automatically generated diagnostic figures**. When the model calibration is finished, the model is run one final time using the `best` parameter set found during the optimisation. The `plot_results` function can then be used to automatically produce more than 10 diagnostic figures (e.g., convergence plots, dot plots, histograms, ECDFs, and simulated vs observed plots). The full set of figures can be inspected with `?plot_results`.

5. The same R wrapper function can later be reused within the `verification()` function to run a subset of the parameter sets used during the optimisation and evaluate their performance over a different temporal period.

This workflow is deliberately generic. It can support models such as [SWAT](#), [SWAT+](#), [Open Source LISFLOOD](#), [MODFLOW](#), [WEAP](#), and other domain-specific tools, as long as the model can be driven by editable inputs, a console-based run command, and readable outputs.

```
out <- hydroPSO(fn = "hydromod",
               control = list(drty.in = "PSO.in"),
               model.FUN=my_R_wrapper_function,
               model.FUN.args = list(exe.fname = "run_model.sh",
                                     out.FUN = "read_model_output",
```

```

out.FUN.args = list(ParamFiles="",
                    ParamRanges="",
                    file = "output.txt"),
gof.FUN = "KGE",
gof.FUN.args = list(method = "2012"),
obs = Qobs
)
)

```

The exact executable, input files and output reader depend on the R-external model. The structure of the calibration remains the same.

7 SWAT+ hydrological model

SWAT+ (Soil and Water Assessment Tool Plus) is an open-source, process-based, semi-distributed hydrological model designed to simulate water quantity and quality dynamics across a wide range of spatial and temporal scales. It represents the terrestrial phase of the hydrological cycle by explicitly modelling surface runoff, infiltration, evapotranspiration, soil water redistribution, lateral flow, groundwater recharge, baseflow, channel routing, and the transport of sediments and nutrients. Owing to this comprehensive process representation, SWAT+ supports integrated assessments of land and water management practices, including irrigation, reservoir operations, crop rotations, fertilisation, and conservation measures, as well as scenario analyses under land-use and climate change conditions (Bieger et al., 2017).

Released in 2015, SWAT+ (Jeffrey G. Arnold et al., 2024) constitutes a major structural redesign of the original SWAT model (J. G. Arnold et al., 1998). While maintaining continuity in core hydrological concepts, SWAT+ introduces a more flexible and modular spatial representation. Watersheds are discretised into subbasins, which are further partitioned into Hydrologic Response Units (HRUs) or alternative landscape units that group areas with homogeneous combinations of land use, soil type, and slope. This structure enables a refined representation of spatial heterogeneity while preserving computational efficiency. The revised input–output architecture and object-oriented data structure improve transparency, facilitate scenario configuration, and enhance compatibility with external tools and reproducible workflows.

The original SWAT model has been widely applied for more than four decades in diverse hydro-climatic regions to simulate streamflow, sediment yield, and nutrient transport under varying environmental conditions and management strategies (Douglas-Mankin et al., 2010; Gassman et al., 2007). Building on this legacy, SWAT+ enhances process consistency, improves numerical stability, and expands flexibility in representing routing networks, reservoirs, and management operations. These developments make the model particularly suitable for large-scale basin applications, long-term impact studies, and decision-support contexts requiring scenario comparison.

In addition to meteorological forcings (e.g., precipitation, temperature, solar radiation, wind speed, and relative humidity) and observed variables for calibration and validation (e.g., streamflow, sediment load, nutrient concentrations), SWAT+ requires a set of spatially explicit input datasets describing topography, land use and management, soil physical and hydraulic properties, and channel characteristics (see [Section Input Data](#)). The quality, resolution, and internal consistency of these datasets exert a first-order control on model performance and predictive reliability.

Table 1 summarises a set of frequently calibrated SWAT+ parameters. The selected parameters primarily influence runoff generation, soil water dynamics, groundwater processes, and channel routing, which are commonly targeted during streamflow calibration.

ID	Description	Units	Process	Range
CN2	Initial SCS curve number for moisture condition II	–	Surface runoff generation	35–98
ALPHA_BF	Baseflow alpha factor (groundwater recession constant)	days ⁻¹	Groundwater recession	0.0–1.0
GW_DELAY	Groundwater delay time	days	Recharge to shallow aquifer	0–500
GWQMN	Threshold water depth in shallow aquifer for return flow	mm	Baseflow initiation	0–5000
GW_REVAP	Groundwater “revap” coefficient	–	Capillary rise from aquifer to root zone	0.02–0.20
REVAPMN	Threshold water depth in shallow aquifer for revap	mm	Groundwater–soil interaction	0–500
SOL_K	Saturated hydraulic conductivity of soil layer	mm h ⁻¹	Infiltration and percolation	0–2000
SOL_AWC	Available water capacity of soil layer	mm mm ⁻¹	Soil water storage	0.01–0.40
ESCO	Soil evaporation compensation factor	–	Soil evaporation	0–1
EPCO	Plant uptake compensation factor	–	Root water uptake	0–1
SURLAG	Surface runoff lag coefficient	days	Runoff timing	0–24
CH_N2	Manning’s n value for main channel	–	Channel routing	0.01–0.30
CH_K2	Effective hydraulic conductivity of channel	mm h ⁻¹	Transmission losses	0–500

Table 1: Parameters used by SWAT+ to represent the different hydrological processes in a catchment.

Parameter ranges shown above reflect typical literature-based or practice-oriented bounds used in calibration studies. Actual feasible intervals should be constrained according to site-specific hydrogeological conditions, soil properties, and physiographic characteristics. A defensible calibration strategy should combine sensitivity analysis, physically plausible parameter bounds, and multi-objective performance metrics to ensure hydrological realism and predictive robustness.

8 Installation

Install the latest stable versions of [hydroPSO](#):

```
install.packages("hydroPSO")
```

Alternatively, you can install the development version of [hydroPSO](#) from [GitHub](#):

```
if (!require(devtools)) install.packages("devtools")
library(devtools)
install_github("hzambran/hydroPSO")
```

Install the latest stable versions of [hydroTSM](#) and [hydroGOF](#). These packages are used to manipulate hydrological time series and evaluate the performance of the simulated streamflow.

```
install.packages("hydroTSM")
install.packages("hydroGOF")
```

9 Model set up

9.1 Loading required packages

The `hydroPSO` package and the `TxtInOut` zip file provide all the R functions, input data and model executable files used in this tutorial. The `hydroTSM` ([Zambrano-Bigiarini, 2026b](#)) and `hydroGOF` ([Zambrano-Bigiarini, 2026a](#)) packages are used to manipulate hydrological time series and compute the modified Kling-Gupta efficiency [KGE'; Gupta et al. (2009); Kling et al. (2012)], respectively. Combining these packages illustrates a typical R-external hydrological workflow: data handling, model execution, objective-function evaluation, calibration, and post-processing within a single reproducible script.

```
library(hydroPSO)
library(hydroTSM)
library(hydroGOF)
```

9.2 General settings

The variable `model.drty` is used as the parent directory where the output files generated during the calibration of the hydrological model will be stored.

```
# This object is defined in the initial setup chunk and can be modified there
# according to your specific local paths.
model.drty <- vignette.drty.in
```

The variable `PSO.drty.out` represents the output directory where `hydroPSO` stores the files generated during the calibration of the `SWAT+` hydrological model. It is not necessary to create this directory before running the calibration because, if it does not exist, it is automatically created by `hydroPSO`. Keeping all optimisation outputs in a dedicated directory makes it easier to inspect parameter sets, objective-function values, model simulations, diagnostic figures, and log files after the calibration has finished.

```
PSO.drty.out <- file.path(model.drty, "PSO.out")
```

The variable `Figures.drty.out` represents the output directory where figures generated during the analysis of the calibration and verification results will be stored.

```
Figures.drty.out <- vignette.figures.drty.out
```

```
# If the output directory selected to store the figures does not exist, it is created:
if (!file.exists(Figures.drty.out)) dir.create(Figures.drty.out, recursive=TRUE)
```

Set up the calibration (1979-1997) and verification (1998-2016) periods. Each period includes one year of model warm-up (see Section 9.2), which allows the internal stores of SWAT+ to adjust before the objective function is evaluated:

```
### Full SWAT+ simulation period
### Warmup + CAL + VER
Sim.Ini <- "1979-01-01"
Sim.Fin <- "2016-12-31"

### Calibration period, without warmup
Cal.Ini <- "1980-01-01"
Cal.Fin <- "1997-12-31"

### Verification period, without warmup
Ver.Ini <- "1999-01-01"
Ver.Fin <- "2016-12-31"
```

The simulation period that will be run by the SWAT+ model is defined in the `time.sim` file. For this tutorial the following values were set up:

- `day_start`: 0, to indicate the first day of the year `yr_start`
- `yr_start`: 1979, to indicate the first year of the simulation.
- `day_end` : 0, to indicate the last day of the year `yr_end`
- `yr_end` : 2016, to indicate the last year of the simulation.
- `step` : 0, to indicate daily time step for simulations

The previous values define the period 01-Jan-1979 to 31-Dec-2016 as the total simulation period run by the SWAT+ hydrological model. Once the model is run for the previous period, the **calibration results** will be read by `hydroPS0` for the period 1979-1997 (19 years), as well as the model **simulated values for the validation period** 1998-2016 (19 years)). This implementation ensures that you do not need to change the `time.sim` file to move from the calibration to the verification period. However, that simplicity has an important trade-off: for every single model run the total execution time will be (much) longer than the actual time required to only calibrate the model. Therefore, if you are only interested in calibrating your model and you do not have enough time, it could be worth to include only the calibration period within your `time.sim` file, calibrate your SWAT+ model with `hydroPS0`, then modify your `time.sim` file to include only the verification period, and then run the `verification` function to analyse a different temporal period.

In the computer where this tutorial is being executed, one single SWAT+ run for the previous period takes 66 seconds to complete.

9.3 Model set up and input data

The study area for this tutorial is a subcatchment of the Trancura River Basin, located in the Araucania Region of southern Chile. The catchment drains into the “Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco” streamflow station (COD.BNA:9414001). This basin provides a useful demonstration case because it combines a long daily hydroclimatic record with hydrological conditions that are suitable for evaluating rainfall-runoff model calibration.

The implementation of the SWAT+ hydrological model in the Trancura River Basin followed the standard procedures described in the `QSWAT+ Manual` and the `SWAT+ Editor` documentation. These tools were used to prepare the spatial discretisation of the catchment, define the model objects, assign the required physical attributes, and generate the final `TxtInOut` directory required by the SWAT+ executable.

Although this tutorial is not focused on the full development of a SWAT+ model from scratch, it is useful to document the main assumptions, input datasets, and structural characteristics of the model used in the example. This information allows readers to understand the hydrological context of the application, reproduce the workflow more transparently, and interpret the calibration results in relation to the catchment

Figure 2: Trancura antes de Llafenco sub-basin. Source: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2025.106851>.

configuration.

9.3.1 Input data

- Precipitation and maximum/minimum air temperature:** The meteorological forcings were obtained from the CR2met gridded product (Boisier, 2023) for the period 01-Jan-1960 to 31-Dec-2024. CR2met provides spatially continuous daily meteorological fields for continental Chile at a spatial resolution of 0.05° . In this application, precipitation and air temperature were used as the main climatic drivers of the water balance, controlling runoff generation, evapotranspiration demand, snow accumulation and melt, and seasonal streamflow variability. Prec
- Digital elevation model (DEM):** The DEM used for watershed delineation was produced by combining information from TanDEM-X ©DLR 2017 and the ALOS PALSAR product (Rosenqvist et al., 2007), resulting in a gridded elevation dataset with a spatial resolution of 12.5 m. The DEM was used to derive the drainage network, subbasin boundaries, channel topology, and terrain attributes required by QSWAT+. The high spatial resolution of the DEM is particularly relevant in Andean and pre-Andean catchments, where topographic gradients strongly influence runoff routing and hydrological connectivity.
- Land use:** Land-use information was obtained from a land-cover product currently under development within the ANID PCI NSFC190018 project, under which this work is framed. Land use is a key input in SWAT+ because it affects interception, evapotranspiration, surface roughness, soil protection, runoff generation, and vegetation-related water fluxes. In this example, the spatial dominance of native temperate forest has a direct influence on the expected hydrological behaviour of the basin.
- Soil:** Soil information was discretised using textural classes derived from a SoilGrids-based product currently under development within the ANID FONDAP 1522A0001 project. This product includes downscaling and adjustment with ground observations for the Chilean territory. Soil texture and hydraulic properties are especially important in SWAT+ because they control infiltration, percolation, plant-available water storage, lateral flow, and groundwater recharge. For the original SoilGrids250m product, see Hengl et al. (2017).

- **Daily streamflows:** Daily streamflow observations for the period 01-Jan-1979 to 31-Dec-2016 were obtained from monitoring records collected by the General Water Bureau of Chile, Dirección General de Aguas (DGA). These data are available through the [Estadísticas estaciones DGA](#) website. In this tutorial, the daily observed streamflow series provides the reference data required to evaluate model performance and to guide the calibration of sensitive hydrological parameters.

9.3.2 Resulting SWAT+ model

Using the datasets described above, a SWAT+ model was developed for the **Trancura antes de Llafenco** sub-basin. This catchment represents a humid, forest-dominated basin in southern Chile, where streamflow dynamics are influenced by strong topographic gradients, seasonal precipitation, snow-related processes in higher-elevation areas, and the storage and release of water through soils, shallow aquifers, and channel routing.

The final model configuration has the following characteristics:

- Area: 1,417.9 km² (141,788 ha)
- Simulation period configured in SWAT+: 1999-2010
- Subbasins: 23
- HRUs: 307
- Channels: 44
- Aquifers: 47
- Routing units / Landscape units: 88 / 88
- Recall objects, including point sources and inlets: 148
- Reservoirs, export coefficients, and delivery ratio objects: not represented (0)
- Predominant land uses: temperate evergreen forest (`frse_tems`, approximately 72%), shrubland (`shrb`, approximately 11%), bare soil (`bsvg`, approximately 7%), grassland (`gras`, approximately 5%), and smaller proportions of cropland (`crdy`) and forest plantations (`euca`) below 3%, with isolated wetlands (`wetw`)
- Predominant soil type: Sandy Loam (SL), hydrological group B, with a total soil depth of 2 m
- Slope bands: not considered

This configuration provides a moderately detailed spatial representation of the catchment, with 23 subbasins and 307 HRUs used to capture the main combinations of land use, soil type, and terrain characteristics. The absence of explicit reservoirs is consistent with a modelling setup focused primarily on natural catchment response, while the representation of channels, aquifers, routing units, and recall objects provides the internal structure required to simulate water movement from hillslopes to the basin outlet.

One additional detail required later in the tutorial is the identifier of the outlet channel. For this specific model configuration, the outlet corresponds to channel number 68, which means that the relevant SWAT+ output should be extracted using `channel_id = 68`.

9.3.3 SWAT+ input files required for this tutorial

The resulting SWAT+ model described above is provided along with this vignette as the `TxtInOut` directory. This directory stores the complete set of input files required by SWAT+ to run the hydrological simulation, including simulation settings, climate definitions, hydrological response units, channel and aquifer objects, management information, calibration files, and the output files generated after each model execution. For the sake of this vignette, it is assumed that the user has already created a valid `TxtInOut` directory using QSWAT+ and the SWAT+ Editor, and that the model can be executed from the command line while working inside that directory.

The SWAT+ executable is operating-system specific. A model setup that runs on GNU/Linux, macOS, or MS Windows requires the corresponding executable file for that platform. Therefore, before running this vignette, the user should copy the appropriate SWAT+ executable from the directory created during the local SWAT+ installation into the same `TxtInOut` directory that contains the model input files. This step is essential because `hydromod()` and `hydroPSO()` will call the executable from R, but the executable itself remains an external program controlled by the operating system.

Providing the model in this form keeps this tutorial focused on the coupling between SWAT+ and the calibration workflow, rather than on GIS preprocessing or model construction. In practical terms, the vignette assumes that the `TxtInOut` directory is already complete, internally consistent, and runnable before `hydroPSO` is used. In future revisions, the final model archive is expected to be distributed through the DOI of the associated Zenodo release, allowing readers to cite and download the exact version used in this tutorial.

9.3.4 Observations

The following piece of code specify the name and ID of the streamflow station measuring the discharges at the catchment's outlet. These values will later be used in figure titles during the analysis of the calibration results:

```
Qobs.stationname <- "Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco"  
Qobs.ID          <- "9414001"
```

Now, we load the daily the observed discharge at the catchment outlet as a single `data.frame` object, covering the period from 01-Jan-1979 to 31-Dec-2016:

```
data(Trancura9414001)
```

Create individual time series for dates and Qobs [m3/s]:

```
dates <- Trancura9414001[, 1]  
Qobs  <- Trancura9414001[, 5]
```

It is important to distinguish between **model simulation** and **model calibration**. To **run** SWAT+, observed discharge values at the catchment outlet are not required. However, to **calibrate** the model, observed discharge values must be available at the same temporal frequency as the simulated values, because they are needed to compute the user-defined goodness-of-fit measure between the model simulations and their corresponding observations.

The following code transform the previously created numeric values and their corresponding dates into `zoo` objects:

```
dates    <- as.Date(dates)  
Qobs.zoo <- zoo(Qobs, dates)
```

Daily discharges simulated by SWAT+ are expressed in m³/s, the same units the observed discharges loaded above.

Plotting the full time series of observed discharges (Qobs):

```
#par(mfrow=c(3,1))
#plot(P.zoo , xlab="Time", col="lightblue", main="Precipitation" , ylab="P [mm/day]")
#grid()
#plot(PET.zoo , xlab="Time", col="darkgreen", main="Potential evaporation", ylab="PET [mm/day]")
#grid()
plot(Qobs.zoo, xlab="Time" , col="blue" , main="Observed streamflows" , ylab="Q, [m3/s]" )
grid()
```


Figure 3: Daily values of precipitation, potential evapotranspiration and streamflows for the Trancura River Basin during the 1970-2016 time period.

9.4 Model parameters for calibration with hydroPSO

This section defines a set of ten SWAT+ parameters selected for automatic calibration with `hydroPSO`. The selected parameters represent dominant hydrological processes controlling runoff generation, soil-water storage, lateral flow, percolation, groundwater recharge, baseflow dynamics, and surface runoff response. Together, they provide a compact but physically meaningful parameter set for streamflow calibration while avoiding an unnecessarily high-dimensional optimization problem.

Instead of allowing `hydroPSO` to directly modify the original SWAT+ input files, the calibration workflow will use the `calibration.cal` file (see details in [Appendix B](#)). This is a model-specific SWAT+ input file designed to streamline the calibration process without altering the original model setup. The `calibration.cal` file allows users to modify selected parameters globally, at the basin level, or for specific Hydrologic Response Units (HRUs), making it suitable for both manual and automatic calibration procedures.

Using `calibration.cal` in combination with `hydroPSO` has two practical advantages. First, the original SWAT+ input files remain unaltered, preserving the baseline model configuration and improving reproducibility. Second, each calibration run is faster because `hydroPSO` only needs to update the calibration file, rather than repeatedly editing the individual model input files listed in `ParamFiles.txt` for each calibrated parameter.

The ten parameters selected for calibration are listed below.

ID	Short description	Units	Archive
awc	Available water capacity	-	soils.sol
k	Saturated hydraulic conductivity	mm/hr	soils.sol
latq_co	Lateral soil flow coefficient, linear component	-	hydrology.hyd
perco	Percolation coefficient	-	hydrology.hyd
revap_min	Threshold aquifer water depth required for revap to occur	m	aquifer.aqu
flo_min	Minimum aquifer storage required to allow return flow	m	aquifer.aqu
alpha_bf	Baseflow recession, or alpha, factor	1/day	aquifer.aqu
revap	Groundwater revap coefficient	-	aquifer.aqu
rchg_dp	Fraction of percolation routed to the deep aquifer	-	aquifer.aqu
CN2	SCS curve number for surface runoff generation	-	cntable.lum

9.5 Running SWAT+ once with hydromod()

For the calibration of SWAT+, or any other hydrological model implemented as an external executable, an R interface must be created to connect the model with `hydroPSO`. In this vignette that interface is provided by `hydromod()`. The function receives one candidate parameter set from the PSO engine, writes those values into the selected model input files, runs the external SWAT+ executable, reads the model output, computes the objective function, and returns the information required by `hydroPSO` to guide the swarm through the parameter space.

This wrapper-function design is one of the main reasons why `hydroPSO` is useful beyond a single model. Once the interface is defined, the same optimisation engine can be applied to other hydrological models, objective functions, transformations, or calibration periods with limited changes to the surrounding workflow.

9.5.1 Wrapper requirements

Any function used as a model wrapper by `hydroPSO` must fulfil the following requirements:

- 1) Its first argument must be named `param.values`, representing the numeric values of the parameters to be optimised.
- 2) One of its arguments must be named `obs`, representing the observed values used to evaluate the simulated streamflow generated by the hydrological model.
- 3) It must return a list object with, at least, the following elements:
 - 3.1) **GoF**: the goodness-of-fit value obtained when the hydrological model is run with `param.values` as the parameter set.
 - 3.2) **sim**: the model output obtained when the hydrological model is run with `param.values` as the parameter set. It must have the same object class and dimensions as the observed values provided by the user in `obs`.

For an R-based model, these requirements are usually implemented in a user-defined function. For an external model such as SWAT+, `hydromod()` already implements this wrapper structure, provided that the user supplies the parameter-mapping files, the executable information, the output-reading function, the observations, and the goodness-of-fit function.

9.5.2 Required variables

The following code defines the minimum set of objects required to test the SWAT+ model through `hydromod()`: the package dependencies, the model and parameter-mapping directories, one trial parameter set, the output-reading function, the observed streamflow series, and the executable command. These are the same objects that will later be reused inside the `hydroPSO` calibration call.

```
library(zoo)
library(hydroGOF)
library(hydroPSO)

# Directory where the external model executable and input/output files live
root.drty <- vignette.drty.in
model.drty <- file.path(root.drty, "TxtInOut")

# hydroPSO parameter-mapping files
param.files <- file.path(root.drty, "PSO.in", "ParamFiles.txt")
param.ranges <- file.path(root.drty, "PSO.in", "ParamRanges.txt")

param.values <- c(0.50000, 0.83500, 0.00750, 0.00000, 155.00000,
                 105.00000, 5.50000, 5.50000, 0.11000, 0.05000)
param.names <- c("perco", "latq_co", "alpha", "cn2", "awc",
```

```

      "k", "flo_min", "revap_min", "revap_co", "deep_seep")
names(param.values) <- param.names

# Function to read the external model output
Rscripts.drty.in  <- file.path(root.drty, "Rfunctions")
swat2zoo.fname.in  <- "swat2zoo.R" # see details in [Appendix A] (#AppendixA)
swat2zoo.fname.full <- file.path(Rscripts.drty.in, swat2zoo.fname.in)
source(swat2zoo.fname.full, echo = TRUE)

##
## > swat2zoo <- function(file.name = "channel_sdmorph_day.txt",
## +   id, first.date = NULL, last.date = NULL, name.col) {
## +   if (!requireNamespace( ... [TRUNCATED]
# Observed values from 1979-01-01 to 2016-12-31
data(Trancura9414001)
dates <- Trancura9414001[, 1]
Qobs <- Trancura9414001[, 5]
dates <- as.Date(dates)
Qobs.zoo <- zoo::zoo(Qobs, dates)
Qobs.zoo.cal <- window(Qobs.zoo, start=Cal.Ini, end=Cal.Fin)

# name of the executable model file, e.g., "model.exe", "model_command", etc.
model.exe.file <- "./rev60.5.7_64rel_unix_like.sh" # see details in Appendix C

file.exists(param.files)

## [1] TRUE
file.exists(param.ranges)

## [1] TRUE
file.exists(file.path(model.drty, model.exe.file))

## [1] TRUE
file.exists(file.path(model.drty, "calibration.cal"))

## [1] TRUE
file.exists(file.path(model.drty, "channel_sd_day.txt"))

## [1] TRUE

```

9.5.3 Minimal hydromod() call

The following call runs SWAT+ once with the trial parameter set. This is the external-model equivalent of a minimal model-wrapper test: if this call returns a simulated time series and a finite goodness-of-fit value, the model-execution chain is ready to be used by hydroPSO. During troubleshooting, `stdout = ""` can be used to print regular messages from the executable; for a quieter vignette run, `stdout = FALSE` suppresses standard output while keeping `stderr = ""` available for error messages.

```
# Run the external model once
out <- hydromod(
  param.values = param.values,
  param.files = param.files,
  param.ranges = param.ranges,
  model.drty = model.drty,
  exe.fname = model.exe.file,
  exe.args = character(),
  stdout= FALSE, # set it to TRUE to identify errors
  stderr="",
  out.FUN = "swat2zoo",
  out.FUN.args = list(
    file.name = "channel_sd_day.txt",
    id = 68,
    name.col = "flo_out",
    first.date = Sim.Ini,
    last.date = Sim.Fin
  ),
  gof.FUN = "KGE",
  gof.FUN.args = list(method = "2012"),
  gof.Ini = Cal.Ini,
  gof.Fin = Cal.Fin,
  date.fmt = "%Y-%m-%d",
  obs = Qobs.zoo,
  verbose = TRUE
) # 'hydromod' END
```

```
##
## =====
## [ 1) Writing new parameter values ... ]
## =====
## =====
## [ 2) Running the model ... ]
## =====
## =====
## [ 3) Extracting simulated values ... ]
## =====
## =====
## [ 4) Computing the goodness of fit ... ]
## =====
## [KGE= 0.5]
```

9.5.4 Diagnostic run before calibration

Before launching a full `hydroPSO` calibration of `SWAT+`, it is strongly recommended to run the external model once with `hydromod()`. This preliminary run acts as a diagnostic test of the complete model-execution chain: parameter writing, model execution, output extraction, and goodness-of-fit computation. In the context of `SWAT+`, this step is particularly important because the model is not an R function but an external executable that depends on a consistent `TxtInOut` directory, valid input files, platform-specific execution permissions, correctly mapped calibration parameters, and readable output files. If any of these elements fails, `hydroPSO` will also fail, but the source of the error will be harder to identify once the optimisation loop has already started.

The `hydromod()` function should therefore be used as a controlled single-model experiment before activating the particle swarm. In this test, the user provides one trial parameter set through `param.values`, which represents a single candidate solution to be written into the `SWAT+` input files. These values are not intended to be optimal. Their purpose is to verify that the selected parameters can be transferred correctly from R to the external model. The files `param.files` and `param.ranges` define this transfer. `param.files` tells `hydromod()` where each parameter must be modified inside the `SWAT+` input structure, whereas `param.ranges` defines the admissible calibration range and the type of change to apply, such as replacement, additive change, or multiplicative change. Testing these files with one controlled parameter set is the simplest way to detect wrong parameter names, incorrect file paths, formatting problems, or parameter values that produce invalid `SWAT+` input files.

The arguments `model.drty`, `exe.fname`, and `exe.args` define how the external model is actually executed. `model.drty` points to the directory where the runnable `SWAT+` setup is located, typically the folder containing the `TxtInOut` files and the corresponding executable or script. `exe.fname` is the command used to run the model, for example a shell script on Linux/macOS or an executable file on Windows. `exe.args` contains optional command-line arguments passed to that executable; it can be left empty when the model is launched without additional options. Running `hydromod()` first confirms that the operating system can find and execute the model, that file permissions are correct, and that the working directory contains all files required by `SWAT+`.

The arguments `stdout` and `stderr` control where the messages produced by the external model are sent when `hydromod()` calls the `SWAT+` executable through R. They follow the same logic used by `base::system2()`. The argument `stdout` controls the standard output stream, which usually contains regular messages printed by the model during execution, such as progress information, file-reading messages, or a normal termination message. The argument `stderr` controls the standard error stream, which usually contains warnings or error messages produced by the executable or the operating system. Possible values include `FALSE`, which discards the corresponding output, and `""`, which prints it directly to the R console.

These two arguments are especially useful during the first configuration of `hydromod()`. By default, `stdout = FALSE`, which means that normal messages printed by `SWAT+` are omitted. This is a convenient setting for large calibration experiments with `hydroPSO`, because thousands of model evaluations would otherwise flood the R console with repetitive messages and make the optimisation output difficult to inspect. However, during the initial test with `hydromod()`, it is recommended to set `stdout = ""`. This allows the user to see whether `SWAT+` actually started, whether it read the expected input files, and whether it reached the end of the simulation. In practice, `stdout = ""` is a simple but effective way to distinguish between a model that is running correctly and a model that silently fails before producing usable outputs.

The default setting `stderr = ""` should usually be preserved during the first `hydromod()` tests, because it prints model or system error messages directly to the R console. This is critical for identifying configuration problems such as a missing executable, insufficient execution permissions, incorrect relative paths, missing `TxtInOut` files, malformed input files, or errors generated internally by `SWAT+`. Once the model-execution chain has been verified, and especially when running `hydroPSO`, the user may decide to keep only the most informative messages or suppress regular output. A useful debugging strategy is therefore to run the first `hydromod()` call with `stdout = ""` and `stderr = ""`, inspect the console carefully, and only move to quieter settings after the external model has been confirmed to execute correctly.

Once SWAT+ has been executed, the next critical step is to read the simulated outputs. This is handled by `out.FUN`, a user-defined R function that extracts the relevant model results from the SWAT+ output files. In a streamflow calibration, this function would typically read the simulated discharge at the basin outlet, using the correct output file, variable name, date range, and `channel_id`. Additional information required by `out.FUN` is passed through `out.FUN.args`; for example, the path to the output file or the identifier of the channel corresponding to the catchment outlet. This step should be tested before calibration because many errors in external-model workflows come not from the model run itself, but from reading the wrong output file, extracting the wrong object, using inconsistent dates, or returning simulations in a format that does not match the observations.

The arguments `obs`, `gof.FUN`, and `gof.FUN.args` complete the diagnostic chain by comparing simulated and observed values. `obs` contains the observed variable used for calibration, such as daily streamflow from the DGA station at the basin outlet. `gof.FUN` defines the performance metric to be optimised, for example `hydroGOF::KGE`, `NSE`, `RMSE`, or another objective function appropriate for the modelling objective. `gof.FUN.args` passes additional options to the selected metric, such as the KGE formulation. A successful `hydromod()` run should return both the simulated values, commonly accessed as `out$sim`, and the goodness-of-fit value, commonly accessed as `out$GoF`. This confirms that the complete model-evaluation workflow is operational before thousands of candidate parameter sets are evaluated by `hydroPSO`.

Running `hydroPSO` directly without first testing `hydromod()` is risky because it mixes two different sources of failure. An error may come from the SWAT+ configuration itself, from incorrect parameter mapping, from a missing or non-executable model command, from an output-reading problem, from incompatible observed and simulated time series, or from the optimisation settings used by `hydroPSO`. By isolating the model-execution step with `hydromod()`, the user can verify that the external model behaves correctly for one parameter set before asking the swarm to explore the full parameter space. In practice, this makes debugging faster, reduces wasted computation, and provides a more reliable foundation for reproducible calibration of SWAT+ with `hydroPSO`.

A practical rule is therefore: first make `hydromod()` run cleanly, then use the same logic inside `hydroPSO`. During the initial diagnostic run, use verbose settings such as `stdout = ""` and `stderr = ""` to expose model messages and errors. During the final calibration, prefer quieter settings, especially `stdout = FALSE`, to avoid unnecessary console output during repeated model evaluations. Once `param.values`, `param.files`, `param.ranges`, `model.drty`, `exe.fname`, `stdout`, `stderr`, `out.FUN`, `obs`, and `gof.FUN` have been verified in a single-run test, the calibration problem becomes much easier to scale up. At that stage, `hydroPSO` can focus on what it is designed to do: efficiently searching the parameter space, updating particles across iterations, and identifying parameter sets that improve the hydrological performance of the SWAT+ model.

9.5.5 Inspecting the diagnostic run

```
sim <- out$sim # simulated values  
gof <- out$GoF # goodness-of-fit value
```

Extract only the simulated streamflows from the full model output:

```
Qsim.zoo.cal <- window(sim, start=Cal.Ini, end=Cal.Fin)
```

Transform the simulated streamflow values from numeric vectors into zoo objects:

```
dates.cal <- time(Qsim.zoo.cal)
```

Graphically compare the observed and simulated time series obtained with this reference parameter set:

```
ggof( sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ylab="Q, [m3/s]", lty=c(1, 1), cex=0.4)
```


Figure 4: Evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

This parameter set improves the simulation relative to the previous diagnostic run, but there is still substantial room for improvement through formal calibration.

10 Calibrating SWAT+ with hydroPSO

When calibrating SWAT+ with hydroPSO, the model simulation period is often longer than the period used to compute the objective function. This is not only acceptable, but usually desirable. A longer SWAT+ simulation period allows the model to initialise internal stores, such as soil moisture, shallow aquifer storage, groundwater contribution, and channel routing states, before the calibration period begins. In the example used here, SWAT+ is configured to simulate from `Sim.Ini = "1979-01-01"` to `Sim.Fin = "2016-12-31"`, whereas the calibration period is restricted to `Cal.Ini = "1980-01-01"` and `Cal.Fin = "1997-12-31"`. This separation is important because the model should be allowed to run over the full period required to produce stable simulated outputs, while the goodness-of-fit value should be computed only over the user-defined calibration window.

The role of `out.FUN` is to extract the relevant simulated variable from the files generated by SWAT+ after each model run. In this example, `out.FUN = "swat2zoo"` tells hydroPSO to use the user-defined function `swat2zoo()` to read the simulated streamflow from a SWAT+ output file and return it as a time series object. This function is the bridge between the external model and R: SWAT+ writes its results to text files, while hydroPSO needs a clean R object containing the simulated values to compare against observations. The companion argument `out.FUN.args` provides the information required by `swat2zoo()` to find and extract the correct output. In the example, `file.name = "channel_sd_day.txt"` identifies the daily channel output file, `id = 68` selects the outlet channel, `name.col = "flo_out"` selects the simulated outflow variable, and `first.date` and `last.date` define the full simulated period covered by the SWAT+ output.

The arguments `first.date = Sim.Ini` and `last.date = Sim.Fin` inside `out.FUN.args` should describe the complete period represented in the SWAT+ output file, not only the calibration period. This distinction is essential. The output-reading function first reconstructs the full simulated time series from the external model output, using the complete simulation dates. Only after that full simulation has been read can hydroPSO subset the simulated and observed series to the calibration period. In practical terms, `out.FUN` and `out.FUN.args` answer the question: “Where are the simulated values, and how should they be read?” They should not be used to define which part of the time series is used for calibration. That task belongs to `gof.Ini` and `gof.Fin`.

The goodness-of-fit calculation is controlled by `gof.FUN`, `gof.FUN.args`, `gof.Ini`, and `gof.Fin`. The argument `gof.FUN = "KGE"` indicates that the Kling-Gupta Efficiency is used as the objective function to evaluate the match between observed and simulated streamflow. The argument `gof.FUN.args = list(method = "2012")` passes additional options to the selected metric, in this case requesting the 2012 formulation of KGE implemented in hydroGOF. The arguments `gof.Ini = Cal.Ini` and `gof.Fin = Cal.Fin` define the exact temporal window over which the objective function is computed. Therefore, even if SWAT+ simulates 1979-2016, hydroPSO evaluates each parameter set only over 1980-1997. This is the recommended way to handle warm-up periods, validation periods, or long model simulations where only a subset of the output should inform calibration.

The argument `date.fmt = "%Y-%m-%d"` tells hydroPSO how to interpret the dates provided in `gof.Ini`, `gof.Fin`, and the time index of the simulated and observed series. This may look like a minor detail, but it is critical for reproducible calibration. If the date format is inconsistent, hydroPSO may fail to subset the series correctly, or worse, compare the wrong dates without an obvious error. The argument `obs` provides the observed time series used as the calibration reference. In the example, the observed daily streamflow is converted to a zoo object, `Qobs.zoo`, with dates as the time index. This is good practice because it allows hydroPSO and hydroGOF to align observations and simulations by date rather than by position alone.

Finally, `verbose` controls how much information is printed while hydroPSO evaluates the model. In `model.FUN.args`, `verbose = FALSE` is appropriate once the output-reading and goodness-of-fit workflow has been tested, because a full calibration may require hundreds or thousands of SWAT+ executions. Excessive messages during each model evaluation can make the optimisation output difficult to inspect and slow down the workflow. During development, however, temporarily using more verbose settings can help verify that `out.FUN` is reading the intended file, that `channel_id = 68` corresponds to the basin outlet, that `flo_out` is the correct simulated variable, and that the overlap between `obs`, `gof.Ini`, and `gof.Fin` is correct. Once these checks are complete, hydroPSO can focus on the calibration task itself: exploring the parameter space

and identifying parameter sets that improve the simulated hydrograph during the selected calibration period.

The following code set up the first basic definitions to be used afterwards during the calibration of SWAT+:

```
library(zoo)
library(hydroGOF)
library(hydroPSO)

root.drty <- vignette.drty.in
model.drty <- file.path(root.drty, "TxtInOut")
PS0.in <- file.path(root.drty, "PS0.in")
PS0.out <- PS0.drty.out

param.files <- file.path(PS0.in, "ParamFiles.txt")
param.ranges <- file.path(PS0.in, "ParamRanges.txt")

Rscripts.drty.in <- file.path(root.drty, "Rfunctions")
swat2zoo.fname.full <- file.path(Rscripts.drty.in, "swat2zoo.R")
source(swat2zoo.fname.full)

data(Trancura9414001)
dates <- as.Date(Trancura9414001[, 1])
Qobs <- Trancura9414001[, 5]
Qobs.zoo <- zoo::zoo(Qobs, dates)

model.exe.file <- "./rev60.5.7_64rel_unix_like.sh"
```

The following code set up `model.FUN.args`, which stores the argument values to be passed to the `hydromod()` function during the calibration of SWAT+:

```
model.FUN.args <- list(param.files = param.files,
                      param.ranges = param.ranges,

                      model.drty = model.drty,

                      exe.fname = model.exe.file,
                      exe.args = character(),

                      out.FUN = "swat2zoo", # See details in Appendix A
                      out.FUN.args = list(file.name = "channel_sd_day.txt",
                                           id = 68,
                                           name.col = "flo_out",
                                           first.date = Sim.Ini,
                                           last.date = Sim.Fin
                                           ),

                      gof.FUN = "KGE",
                      gof.FUN.args = list(method = "2012"),

                      gof.Ini = Cal.Ini,
                      gof.Fin = Cal.Fin,
                      date.fmt = "%Y-%m-%d",

                      obs = Qobs.zoo,

                      verbose = FALSE
                      )
```

The following code runs the `hydroPSO()` function to calibrate the 10 user-defined parameters of SWAT+:

```
set.seed(123)

out <- hydroPSO(fn = "hydromod",

               model.FUN = "hydromod",
               model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args,

               control = list(drty.in = PSO.in,
                             drty.out = PSO.out,

                             parallel = "parallel",
                             par.nodes = 5,
                             par.pkgs = c("hydroPSO", "hydroGOF", "hydroTSM",
                                           "zoo", "data.table"),

                             MinMax = "max",

                             npart = 48, # Use 2 for a quick testing the first time
                             maxit = 40, # Use 2 for a quick testing the first time

                             write2disk = TRUE,
                             verbose = TRUE,
                             REPORT = 1
               )
)
```

In the previous code chunk, the arguments passed to `hydroPSO` are briefly explained below (more information can be found with `?hydroPSO`):

- a) **fn**: character string used to tell `hydroPSO` that it will optimise an R-external hydrological model.
- b) **lower**: numeric vector defining the lower boundaries of the model parameters.
- c) **upper**: numeric vector defining the upper boundaries of the model parameters.
- d) **method**: character string defining the PSO algorithm used to calibrate the hydrological model.
- e) **model.FUN**: R function used to run the hydrological model, returning model simulations and their corresponding goodness-of-fit value while fulfilling the three requirements mentioned in Section 9.2.
- f) **model.FUN.args**: list object containing all arguments used to run the hydrological model, in addition to **param.values**.
- g) **control**: list object containing the arguments used to fine-tune the calibration with `hydroPSO`. The arguments passed to **control** affect how `hydroPSO` explores the parameter space and how optimisation outputs are written. Particular attention should be given to the following:
 - *drty.out*: character, with the full path to directory that will store the output files of `hydroPSO`, only used when `write2disk=FALSE`. By default `drty.out="PSO.out"` which is looked for within the current working directory. If `drty.out` does not exist, it is automatically created by `hydroPSO` with an informative warning message.
 - *write2disk*: logical, indicates whether the output files will be written to the disk or not. By default `write2disk=TRUE`. If you are only interested in the *optimum* parameter set found by `hydroPSO` and the corresponding simulated values obtained when running SWAT+ with that parameter set, you should set `write2disk=FALSE`, to reduce the storage used in your computer and to reduce

the total computation time (because internal files are not written to disk). However, if you set `write2disk=FALSE` you will not be able to use the `plot_results` function, because it requires the internal files created by `hydroPSO` when `write2disk=TRUE`.

- *MinMax*: character string indicating whether the calibration solves a maximisation or minimisation problem. Valid values are `c('min', 'max')`. The default value is `"min"`.
- *npart*: numeric value defining the number of particles in the swarm. By default, `npart=NA`, which means that the swarm size depends on the selected method: `npart=ceiling(10+2*sqrt(n))2` when `method='sps02007'`, or `npart=40` otherwise.
- *maxit*: numeric, maximum number of iterations. By default `maxit=1000`.
- *Xini.type*: character, indicates how to initialise the particles' positions in the swarm within the ranges defined by `lower` and `upper`. By default `Xini.type='random'` (random initialisation of positions). However, you might want to try `Xini.type='lhs'` (Latin Hypercube initialisation), or `Xini.type='sobol'` (since `hydroPSO>=0.6`, for quasi-random initialisation of particle's positions using uniform Sobol low discrepancy numbers).
- *boundary.wall*: sometimes PSO fails to keep particles within the valid search space. This argument addresses this by defining exactly how out-of-bounds particles are managed. The specific values it can take are:
 - `NA`: The default setting. It automatically applies either `absorbing2007` or `absorbing2011` depending on the chosen optimisation method.
 - `absorbing2011`: Clamps the particle's position to the boundary edge but flexibly modifies its velocity, allowing it to smoothly 'slide' along the wall rather than stopping completely.
 - `absorbing2007`: A strict clamp that locks the particle to the edge and zeroes its velocity. The particle remains stuck without momentum until algorithmic forces pull it back inside.
 - `reflecting`: Acts as a perfectly elastic surface. It mirrors the particle back inside and exactly reverses its velocity, preserving kinetic energy for continuous, aggressive exploration.
 - `damping`: Functions as an inelastic collision. It reflects the particle back into the space but applies a random reduction to its reversed velocity to bleed off kinetic energy and prevent endless oscillation.
 - `invisible`: Mathematically ignores the boundaries, allowing particles to fly freely outside without altering position or velocity. Out-of-bounds fitness is not evaluated; the particle relies on the attraction of its historical bests to eventually return.
- *normalise*: logical, indicates whether the parameter values have to be normalised to the `[0,1]` interval during the optimisation or not. It is recommended to use this option when the search space is not an hypercube. By default `normalise=FALSE`.
- *reltol*: numeric, relative convergence tolerance. By default to `reltol=sqrt(.Machine$double.eps)`, typically, about `1e-8`.
- *REPORT*: numeric, indicates the frequency of report messages printed to the screen. Default to every 100 iterations. Only used when `verbose=TRUE`.
- *parallel*: character, indicates how to parallelise `hydroPSO`. By default `parallel="none"`. Other possible values are: `parallel="parallel"` (for unix-alike machines) and `parallel="parallelWin"` (for MS Windows machines).
- *par.nnodes*: numeric, indicates the number of cores/CPU's to be used in the local multi-core machine, or the number of nodes to be used in the network cluster. By default `par.nnodes=NA`, which assigns `par.nnodes=parallel::detectCores()` only when `parallel!="none"`.
- *par.pkgs*: list of package names (as characters) that need to be loaded on each node for allowing the objective function `fn` to be evaluated. By default `par.pkgs=list()`. Used only when

²`n` is the number of model parameters being calibrated.

```
parallel="parallelWin".
```

The maximum number of model evaluations during calibration is approximately `npart * maxit`, and the **total execution time** depends on both the cost of one model run and the number of evaluations required by the optimisation. This makes the choice of swarm size (`npart`) and the maximum number of iterations (`maxit`) a practical compromise between search robustness and computational cost.

Using `npart=40` should be good enough for most model applications. However, if the number of parameters of your model is ~ 10 or more, I suggest to **explore the use of a larger number of particles in combination with a lower number of model runs** (e.g., `npart=80` and `maxit=50`). The later ensures that `hydroPSO` will have enough number of particles to effectively tackle the *curse of dimensionality*, and help to reduce premature convergence, which is particularly relevant for hydrological models affected by parameter interactions, threshold behaviour, and equifinality.

10.1 Subsetting for the calibration period

For the calibration of `SWAT+` with `hydroPSO`, only part of the available input time series is used. The remaining period is reserved for independent verification, which provides a more robust assessment of the calibrated parameter set:

Because the model outputs returned by `SWAT+` cover the time period from `Sim.Ini` to `Sim.Fin`, the observations (`Qobs`) must be subset to the same simulation period before they are compared with the simulated streamflows:

```
Qobs.zoo      <- zoo::zoo(Qobs, dates)
Qobs.zoo.cal <- window(Qobs.zoo, start=Cal.Ini, end=Cal.Fin)
```

Store the dates associated with the period used to evaluate the calibration outputs:

```
dates.cal <- time(Qobs.zoo.cal)
```

10.2 Basic analysis of calibration results

Inspect the *best* parameter set obtained during calibration and its corresponding goodness-of-fit value:

```
# Reading the 'best' parameter set and its model performance
# obtained during calibration

best.fname.in <- file.path(PSO.drty.out, "BestParameterSet.txt")
out           <- read_best(file=best.fname.in, verbose=TRUE)

##

## [ Reading the file 'BestParameterSet.txt' ... ]

best.param.cal <- out[["best.param.values"]]
best.param.cal <- as.numeric(best.param.cal[1, ])
names(best.param.cal) <- names(out[["best.param.values"]])
best.gof.cal   <- out[["best.param.gof"]]
```

The variables required to run SWAT+ were defined earlier (i.e., `model.FUN.args`). The model can now be run with the *best* parameter set obtained during calibration:

```
hydromod.args <- modifyList(model.FUN.args,
                             list(param.values = best.param.cal,
                                   verbose=TRUE # To see informative hydroPSO messages
                                   #,stdout= "" # To see SWAT+ messages
                                   )
                             ) # 'hydromod.args' END
modeloutput <- do.call(hydromod, hydromod.args)
```

```
##
## =====
## [ 1) Writing new parameter values ...      ]
## =====
## =====
## [ 2) Running the model ...                ]
## =====
## =====
## [ 3) Extracting simulated values ...       ]
## =====
## =====
## [ 4) Computing the goodness of fit ...     ]
## =====
## [KGE= 0.776]
sim <- modeloutput$sim # simulated values
gof <- modeloutput$GoF # goodness-of-fit value
```

Transform the numeric model output into a zoo object:

```
Qsim.zoo.cal <- window(sim, start=Cal.Ini, end=Cal.Fin)
```

Defining a customised title for the following figures:

```
main <- paste0("SWAT+: ", Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")")
```

Graphical comparison between the **daily observations and simulated time series** obtained with the *best* parameter set for the calibration period, excluding the warm-up period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, main=main, ylab="Q, [m3/s]", cex=0.3, lty=c(1,1) )
```

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Figure 5: Graphical comparison of streamflows simulated by extttSWAT+ during the calibration period using several performance indices.

The calibrated parameter set produces a clearer improvement relative to the preliminary diagnostic runs based on average and reference parameter values.

Graphical comparison between **daily** and **monthly** simulated ($Q_{sim.zoo.cal}$) and observed ($Q_{obs.zoo.cal}$) values for the calibration period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ftype="dm",
     FUN=mean, main=main, ylab="Q, [m3/s]", cex=0.4, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 6: Daily and monthly evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

Graphical comparison between **monthly** and **annual** simulated and observed values for the calibration period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ftype="ma", pt.style="bar",
     FUN=mean, main=main, ylab="Q, [m3/s]", cex=0.4, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 7: Monthly and annual evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

Graphical comparison between **seasonal** simulated and observed values for the calibration period, with one plot for each season:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ftype="seasonal", ylab="Q, [m3/s]",
     season.names=c("Summer", "Autumn", "Winter", "Spring"),
     FUN=mean, main=main, cex.main=2)
```


Figure 8: Seasonal evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

Compute the **daily residuals** for the calibration period:

```
residuals <- Qsim.zoo.cal - Qobs.zoo.cal
```

Plotting **daily**, **monthly**, and **annual** time series, boxplots, and histograms of the residuals for the calibration period:

```
hydroplot(residuals, FUN=mean, var.unit="mm")
```


Figure 9: Analysis of the residuals (simulations - observations) for the calibration period at the daily, monthly, and annual temporal scales.

Plotting **seasonal** time series and boxplots of the residuals for the calibration period:

```
hydroplot(residuals, FUN=mean, pfreq="seasonal",
          season.names=c("Summer", "Autumn", "Winter", "Spring"),
          h=0, main=main, cex.main=2)
```


Figure 10: Analysis of the residuals (simulations - observations) for the calibration period at the seasonal scale.

10.3 Plotting calibration results

Defining a customised title for all figures in this section:

```
main <- paste0("SWAT+: ", Qobs.stationname, " (" , Qobs.ID, ")")
```

10.3.1 Basic plotting

The function `plot_results`, included in `hydroPSO`, can automatically produce several diagnostic figures to support the evaluation of calibration results. Internally, it calls `read_results` and then generates figures that summarise parameter distributions, objective-function behaviour, convergence, and the agreement between observed and simulated values. These diagnostics are useful because they move the calibration analysis beyond a single best value and help identify parameter interactions, equifinality, and possible structural limitations of the model. The function can produce the following eleven (11) figures:

- 1) Dotty plots of parameter values.
- 2) Histograms of parameter values.
- 3) Boxplots of parameter values.
- 4) Correlation matrix among parameter values (optional).
- 5) Empirical CDFs of parameter values.
- 6) Parameter values vs Number of Model Evaluations.
- 7) (pseudo) 3D dotty plots of (selected) parameter values.
- 8) GoF for each particle against the Number of Model Evaluations.
- 9) Velocity values vs Number of Model Evaluations.
- 10a) Scatterplot between Best Simulated values and Observations (OPTIONAL, only if `MinMax` is provided).
- 10b) Empirical CDFs for model output (only produced if `obs` is NOT a zoo object).
- 10b) ggof (See `?ggof`) between Best Simulated values and Observations (OPTIONAL, only if `obs` is a zoo object).
- 10d) Empirical CDFs for selected quantiles of model output (OPTIONAL, only if `obs` is a zoo object).
- 11) Convergence Measures (`Gbest` and `normSwarmRadius`) vs Iteration Number.

Basic automatic plotting of the calibration results to the current graphics device, usually the screen, can be obtained with:

```
plot_results(drty.out=PS0.drty.out)
```

10.3.2 Advanced plotting

Although the automatic plotting of calibration results may be sufficient for many applications, it is advisable to read `?plot_results` and customise its arguments to obtain figures that meet the needs of a specific study, report, or publication:

```
plot_results(drty.out=PSO.drty.out, # directory that stores all the calibration outputs
            do.png=TRUE,           # plots go to PNG figures instead of to the screen
            params.png.width=900,  # 7 inches equals 630 pixels at 90 DPI. 900
            params.png.height=900, # 7 inches equals 630 pixels at 90 DPI. 1500
            MinMax="max",          # 'best' parameter set is the one with the highest GoF
            beh.thr=0.3,           # behavioural parameter sets (with GoF >= 0.3 )
            ftype="dm",           # to produce daily and monthly figures of 'sim' vs 'obs'
            nrows=2,              # number of rows in parameter figures (histograms,...)
            FUN=mean,              # function used to compute monthly values
            do.pairs=TRUE,         # correlation plot among parameters and GoF
            gof.name="KGE2012",    # name used for axis titles in parameter figures
            legend.pos="right",    # position of the legend in the convergence plot
            main=main              # user-defined title for most of the output figures
        )
```

```
## [                                     ]
## [           Reading output files ...   ]
## [                                     ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 1440 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 1439 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Velocities.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 1440 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 1439 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Model_out.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 1440 ]
## [ Number of model outputs for each parameter set ('nsim'): 6575 ]
## [ Number of behavioural model outputs           : 1439 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'ConvergenceMeasures.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of iterations: 30 ]
## [ Number of iterations with Gbest >= 0.3: 30 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles_GofPerIter.txt' ... ]
## [ Number of particles : 48 ]
```

```

## [ Number of iterations: 30 ]
## [                               ]
## [           Plotting ...       ]
## [                               ]
## [ Plotting convergence measures into 'ConvergenceMeasures.png' ... ]
##
## [ Plotting dotty plots for parameter values into 'Params_DottyPlots.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting histograms for parameter values into 'Params_Histograms.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting boxplots for parameter values into 'Params_Boxplots.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting correlation matrix for parameter values into 'Params_Pairs.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting empirical CDFs for parameter values into 'Params_ECDFs.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting parameter values vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Params_ValuesPerRun.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting 3D dotty plots for parameter values into 'Params_dp3d.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting GoF for each particle vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Particles_GofPerIter.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting velocity values vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Velocities_ValuePerRun.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting best simulated values vs observations into 'ModelOut_BestSim_vs_Obs-Corr.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting best simulated values vs observations into 'ModelOut_BestSim_vs_Obs-ggof.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting ECDFs of simulated quantiles vs observations into 'ModelOut_Quantiles.png' ... ]
## [ Computing un-weighted quantiles for each ROW of 'sim' ... ]
## |                               |

```

The figures generated by the previous call to `plot_results` are **not discussed in detail in this tutorial**. They are provided as examples of the diagnostic material that `hydroPSO` can generate automatically to support scientific reporting and model evaluation. Additional discussions of these outputs can be found in Rojas & Zambrano-Bigiarini (2012), Zambrano-Bigiarini & Rojas (2013), Abdelaziz & Zambrano-Bigiarini (2014), and Abdelaziz et al. (2019).

10.3.2.1 Convergence along iterations

This figure shows the change in the **objective function** (black line) and the change in the **normalised swarm radius** (a measure of swarm spread on the search space) along with the number of iterations used in the optimisation. This figure can be used to obtain a founded guess about the minimum number of iterations required to obtain a satisfactory value of the objective function.

Figure 11: Evolution of global optimum (i.e., KGE2012) and the normalized swarm radius against the number of iterations.

10.3.2.2 Histograms

This figure shows **histograms** of parameter values considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation.

Figure 12: Histograms of user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$) versus parameter values. The vertical red line indicates the optimum parameter value. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

10.3.2.3 Boxplots

This figure shows **boxplots** of parameter values considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The horizontal red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation.

Figure 13: Box-and-whisker plots (or boxplots) of user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$) versus parameter values. The horizontal red line indicates the optimum parameter value found during the optimisation. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

10.3.2.4 Dotty plots

This figure shows **dotty plots** of parameter values versus the objective function, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation, whereas the horizontal red line shows the corresponding best model performance.

Figure 14: Dotty plots showing the model performance of behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$) versus parameter values. The vertical red line indicates the optimum parameter value found during the optimisation, whereas the horizontal red line shows the corresponding best model performance. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

10.3.2.5 Empirical CDFs

This figure shows **empirical CDFs** of parameter values, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets (`KGE2012 >= beh.thr`). Horizontal grey dotted lines represent a cumulative probability equal to 0.5 (median of the distribution). Vertical grey dotted lines represent the parameter value corresponding to a cumulative probability equal to 0.5 (its value is shown in the upper part of each figure).

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Figure 15: Empirical CDFs (continuous black lines) of parameter values. Horizontal gray dotted lines represent a cumulative probability equal to 0.5 (median of the distribution). Vertical gray dotted lines represent the parameter value corresponding to a cumulative probability equal to 0.5 (its value is shown in the upper part of each figure).

10.3.2.6 3D dotty plots

This figure shows a scatter-based diagnostic plot (aka **pseudo three-dimensional dotty plots**) to explore the relationship between pairs of model parameters and a goodness-of-fit (GOF) metric, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh. thr}$). Regions with blue (red) colours illustrate parameter ranges where the interaction of two parameters lead to high (low) model performance. This function is particularly useful in hydrological modelling to assess parameter interactions, equifinality, and behavioural regions after calibration or Monte Carlo simulation.

Figure 16: Three-dimensional dotty plots to explore the relationship between pairs of model parameters and the goodness-of-fit (GOF) metric.

10.3.2.7 Correlation matrix

This figure shows **correlation matrix** between parameters and model performance (KGE2012), considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh. thr}$). Horizontal and vertical axes show the physical range used for the calibration of each parameter. Red curved lines represents are fitted to all the pair of points using a lowess smoother, i.e., a locally-weighted polynomial regression.

Figure 17: Correlation matrix between parameters and model performance (KGE2012). Horizontal and vertical axes show the physical range used for the calibration of each parameter. Red curved lines are fitted to all pairs of points using a lowess smoother, i.e., a locally-weighted polynomial regression.

10.3.2.8 Daily and monthly evaluation

This figure shows a **comparison of daily** (upper panel) and **monthly** (lower panel) **streamflows**, obtained with the *best* parameter set obtained during the optimisation, against their corresponding observed counterparts.

Figure 18: Comparison of daily (upper panel) and monthly (lower panel) streamflows obtained with the 'best' parameter set and their corresponding observed counterparts.

10.3.2.9 Scatterplot of daily values

This figure shows a **Scatterplot** comparing observed streamflows against the simulated values obtained with the *best* parameter set obtained during the optimisation.

Figure 19: Scatterplot of daily streamflows obtained with the 'best' parameter set obtained during calibration and their corresponding observed counterparts.

10.3.2.10 Evaluation of low, medium and high streamflows

This figure shows **empirical CDFs** (blue lines) for 5, 50 and 95 quantiles of simulated discharges obtained by SWAT+ during the calibration period. The previous quantiles were selected as representative of low, medium and high streamflows, respectively. Vertical black-dotted lines represent the observed 5, 50 and 95 quantiles, while vertical grey-dotted lines indicate the median of the simulated quantiles. Therefore, this figure is useful to assess the bias of model results in the low, medium and high part of the simulates time series.

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Figure 20: Empirical CDFs (blue lines) for 5, 50 and 95 quantiles of simulated discharges obtained by extttSWAT+ during the calibration period. Vertical black-dotted lines represent the observed quantiles, while vertical grey-dotted lines indicate the median of the simulated quantiles.

10.3.3 Plotting only some (more sensitive) parameters

In addition to what was mentioned in the previous (Section 10.2), you can customise the `plot_results` function a bit further by plotting only **the most sensitive model parameters** obtained during the calibration, in order to analyse their interactions and explore whether it would be a good idea to reduce some parameters in a subsequent calibration round.

You can utilize the empirical cumulative distribution functions (ECDFs) of model parameters extracted from `hydroPSO` calibration archives to identify the most sensitive and identifiable parameters. For each parameter, plot and compare the ECDF of the behavioural (acceptable) parameter sets against the ECDF of the initial prior distribution—which appears as a 1:1 diagonal line if a uniform distribution was used for sampling. Parameters showing a strong deviation from this prior line have been heavily conditioned by the calibration process, indicating high identifiability Hornberger & Spear (1981). To formally evaluate sensitivity, you should compare the separation between the behavioural and non-behavioural ECDFs. A pronounced separation or narrowing of these curves indicates that the parameter heavily influences model performance, rendering it sensitive and well-constrained. Conversely, if the curves nearly overlap, the parameter is insensitive to the chosen evaluation criteria and can be safely fixed or excluded from subsequent calibration stages.

Based on the results presented in the previous diagnostic plots, we will use the argument `param.names` to create interaction figures only for a reduced set of parameters: `perco`, `latq_co`, `alpha_bf`, `CN2`, `awc`, and `k`. These parameters are used here as an illustrative subset of potentially influential controls on percolation, lateral flow, groundwater recession, surface runoff generation, soil-water storage, and saturated hydraulic conductivity. We will also use the argument `dp3d.names` to create three-dimensional dotty plots only for `perco`, `alpha_bf`, `CN2`, and `k`: `DDF`, `LPrat`, `FC`, `k0`, `lsuz`, `croute`, which were considered as the most sensitive parameters for this particular case study, based on expert judgement. Also, we will use the argument `dp3d.names` to create figures only for the `DDF`, `FC`, `k0` and `croute` parameters:

```
plot_results(drty.out=PSO.drty.out, # directory that stores all the calibration outputs
  param.names= c("perco", "cn2", "latq_co", "alpha", "flo_min", "k"),
  dp3d.names= c("perco", "alpha", "cn2", "flo_min"),
  do.png=TRUE, # plots go to PNG figures instead of to the screen
  params.png.width=855, # 7 inches equals 630 pixels at 90 DPI. 900
  params.png.height=855, # 9.5 inches equals 855 pixels at 90 DPI. 1500
  MinMax="max", # 'best' parameter set is the one with the highest GoF
  beh.thr=0.3, # behavioural parameter sets (with GoF >= 0.3 )
  ftype="dm", # to produce daily and monthly figures of 'sim' vs 'obs'
  #nrows=5, # number of rows in parameter figures (histograms,...)
  FUN=mean, # function used to compute monthly values
  do.pairs=TRUE, # correlation plot among parameters and GoF
  gof.name="KGE2012", # name used for axis titles in parameter figures
  legend.pos="right", # position of the legend in the convergence plot
  main=main, # user-defined title for most of the output figures
  dotty.png.fname = "Params_DottyPlots-Reduced.png",
  hist.png.fname = "Params_Histograms-Reduced.png",
  bxp.png.fname = "Params_Boxplots-Reduced.png",
  ecdf.png.fname = "Params_ECDFs-Reduced.png",
  pruns.png.fname = "Params_ValuesPerRun-Reduced.png", #not used
  dp3d.png.fname = "Params_dp3d-Reduced.png"
)
```

```
## [ ]
## [ Reading output files ... ]
## [ ]
##
```

```

## [ Reading the file 'Particles.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 1440 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 1439 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Velocities.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 1440 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 1439 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Model_out.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 1440 ]
## [ Number of model outputs for each parameter set ('nsim'): 6575 ]
## [ Number of behavioural model outputs          : 1439 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'ConvergenceMeasures.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of iterations: 30 ]
## [ Number of iterations with Gbest >= 0.3: 30 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles_GofPerIter.txt' ... ]
## [ Number of particles : 48 ]
## [ Number of iterations: 30 ]
## [
## [           Plotting ...
## [
## [ Plotting convergence measures into 'ConvergenceMeasures.png' ... ]
##
## [ Plotting dotty plots for parameter values into 'Params_DottyPlots-Reduced.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting histograms for parameter values into 'Params_Histograms-Reduced.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting boxplots for parameter values into 'Params_Boxplots-Reduced.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting correlation matrix for parameter values into 'Params_Pairs.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting empirical CDFs for parameter values into 'Params_ECDFs-Reduced.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting parameter values vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Params_ValuesPerRun-Reduced.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting 3D dotty plots for parameter values into 'Params_dp3d-Reduced.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting GoF for each particle vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Particles_GofPerIter.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting velocity values vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Velocities_ValuePerRun.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting best simulated values vs observations into 'ModelOut_BestSim_vs_Obs-Corr.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting best simulated values vs observations into 'ModelOut_BestSim_vs_Obs-ggof.png' ... ]

```

```
## [ Plotting ECDFs of simulated quantiles vs observations into 'ModelOut_Quantiles.png' ... ]  
## [ Computing un-weighted quantiles for each ROW of 'sim' ... ]  
## |
```

10.3.3.1 Histograms

This figure shows **histograms** of sensitive model parameters, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation.

Figure 21: Histograms of parameter values for user-defined behavioural and sensitive parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum parameter value. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

10.3.3.2 Boxplots

This figure shows **boxplots** of sensitive model parameters, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The horizontal red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation.

Figure 22: Box-and-whisker plots (or boxplots) of sensitive parameter values for user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The horizontal red line indicates the optimum parameter value found during the optimisation. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

10.3.3.3 Dotty plots

This figure shows **dotty plots** of sensitive model parameters versus the objective function, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation, whereas the horizontal red line shows the corresponding best model performance.

Figure 23: Dotty plots showing the model performance of behavioural sensitive parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum parameter value found during the optimisation, whereas the horizontal red line shows the corresponding best model performance. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

10.3.3.4 Empirical CDFs

This figure shows **empirical CDFs** of sensitive parameter values, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets (`KGE2012 >= beh_thr`). Horizontal grey dotted lines represent a cumulative probability equal to 0.5 (median of the distribution). Vertical grey dotted lines represent the parameter value corresponding to a cumulative probability equal to 0.5 (its value is shown in the upper part of each figure).

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Figure 24: Empirical CDFs (continuous black lines) of sensitive parameter values. Horizontal grey dotted lines represent a cumulative probability equal to 0.5, and vertical grey dotted lines represent the parameter value corresponding to a cumulative probability equal to 0.5.

10.3.3.5 3D dotted plots

This figure shows a scatter-based diagnostic plot (aka **pseudo-three-dimensional dotted plots**) to explore the relationship between pairs of sensitive model parameters and a goodness-of-fit (GOF) metric, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). Regions with blue (red) colours illustrate parameter ranges where the interaction of two parameters lead to high (low) model performance. This function is particularly useful in hydrological modelling to assess parameter interactions, equifinality, and behavioural regions after calibration or Monte Carlo simulation.

Figure 25: Three-dimensional dotted plots to explore the relationship between pairs of sensitive model parameters and the goodness-of-fit (GOF) metric.

10.4 Uncertainty analysis of calibration results

If you are not familiar with uncertainty analysis, you might be interested in Refsgaard et al. (2007), who review the terminology and typology of uncertainty, its interaction with the broader water management process and the role of uncertainty at different stages in the modelling processes.

10.4.1 Reading all calibration results

To proceed with the uncertainty analysis, read the calibration results generated by hydroPSO during the optimisation. In this tutorial, the focus is on **behavioural parameter sets** (Beven, 2006; Beven & Binley, 1992; Beven & Freer, 2001), defined here by an arbitrary user-selected goodness-of-fit threshold. For this example, `beh.thr=0.3` is used. Setting `beh.thr=0.3` and `MinMax='max'` considers as behavioural all parameter sets with goodness-of-fit values higher than the selected threshold:

```
res <- read_results(drty.out = PSO.drty.out, MinMax = "max", beh.thr = 0.3)
```

```
## [ ]
## [ Reading output files ... ]
## [ ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 1440 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 1439 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Velocities.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 1440 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 1439 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Model_out.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 1440 ]
## [ Number of model outputs for each parameter set ('nsim'): 6575 ]
## [ Number of behavioural model outputs : 1439 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'ConvergenceMeasures.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of iterations: 30 ]
## [ Number of iterations with Gbest >= 0.3: 30 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles_GofPerIter.txt' ... ]
## [ Number of particles : 48 ]
## [ Number of iterations: 30 ]
```

The next code chunk assigns all the behavioural parameter sets obtained during calibration (*params*), i.e., those with goodness-of-fit value higher than `beh.thr`; the goodness-of-fit value of each behavioural parameter set (*gofs*), the model outputs (i.e., streamflows for the SWAT+ case) corresponding to each behavioural parameter set (*Qsims*), the model output corresponding to the best parameter set obtained during calibration (*model.best*), and the observed values used in the calibration to compute the goodness-of-fit value (*model.obs*):

```
params    <- res[["params"]]
gofs      <- res[["gofs"]]
Qsims     <- res[["model.values"]]
model.best <- res[["model.best"]]
model.obs <- res[["model.obs"]]
```

10.4.2 Weighted quantiles of parameter values

Weighted quantiles of model parameters provide an estimate of parameter uncertainty based on the behavioural parameter sets obtained during calibration and their corresponding goodness-of-fit values. User-defined weighted quantiles for each model parameter are obtained by multiplying the standard quantile derived for each model parameter based on all the behavioural parameter sets (i.e., for each column in `params`) by the corresponding goodness-of-fit value obtained by the parameter set (*gofs*)³. In this tutorial, the `wquantile` function from `hydroPS0` is used to compute the 2.5, 50, and 97.5 weighted quantiles for each model parameter, by setting `probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975)`:

```
params.025.50.975 <- wquantile(params, weights=gofs, byrow=FALSE, probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975),
                               normwt=TRUE, verbose=FALSE)
```

It may be useful to compare the *best* parameter set found during calibration with the median of the weighted behavioural parameter sets. In the following code chunk, a new column is added to `params.025.50.975`, immediately after the median (quantile 50):

```
params.025.50.best.975 <- cbind(params.025.50.975[, c(1,2)],
                                Best=as.numeric(best.param.cal),
                                params.025.50.975[, 3] )
colnames(params.025.50.best.975)[4] <- "97.5%"
round( params.025.50.best.975, 2)
```

FALSE	2.5%	50%	Best	97.5%
FALSE perco	0.00	0.59	1.00	1.00
FALSE latq_co	0.75	0.83	0.77	0.92
FALSE alpha	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01
FALSE cn2	-18.81	-0.73	1.93	17.71
FALSE awc	17.03	130.88	39.57	290.15
FALSE k	17.81	105.07	28.53	178.48
FALSE flo_min	1.11	5.61	9.97	9.92
FALSE revap_min	1.06	5.08	8.65	9.90
FALSE revap_co	0.02	0.11	0.09	0.20
FALSE deep_seep	0.00	0.05	0.06	0.10

10.4.3 Weighted quantiles of model simulations

Weighted quantiles of model simulations provide an estimate of uncertainty for each model-simulated value (i.e., each daily streamflow), using the goodness-of-fit values obtained for the complete simulated time series. User-defined weighted quantiles for each model simulation are obtained by combining the ensemble of simulations in `Qsims` with their corresponding goodness-of-fit values in `gofs`. In this tutorial, the `wquantile`

³For more information about the computation of the weighted quantiles, please read `?wtd.stats`.

function from hydroPSO is used to compute the 2.5, 50, and 97.5 weighted quantiles for each value simulated by the model, by setting `probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975)`:

```
Qsim.025.q50.q975 <- wquantile(Qsims, weights=gofs, byrow=FALSE, probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975),
                              normwt=TRUE, verbose=FALSE)
round( head(Qsim.025.q50.q975), 3)
```

```
FALSE      2.5%   50%  97.5%
FALSE Sim1  8.806 12.390 49.290
FALSE Sim2  8.094 11.460 48.599
FALSE Sim3  6.515 10.620 48.165
FALSE Sim4  6.027  9.897 47.614
FALSE Sim5  5.738  9.261 46.911
FALSE Sim6  5.480  8.659 46.293
```

To plot the uncertainty bounds for each model-simulated value, transform the weighted quantiles 2.5 and 97.5 into zoo objects:

```
dates.cal <- dip(Cal.Ini, Cal.Fin)
q025      <- zoo(Qsim.025.q50.q975[,1], dates.cal)
q975      <- zoo(Qsim.025.q50.q975[,3], dates.cal)
```

10.4.4 P-factor and R-factor

Compute the **P-factor** (Abbaspour et al., 2009; Schuol et al., 2008), which represents the percentage of observations that are within the user-defined uncertainty bounds:

```
( pf <- hydroGOF::pfactor(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, na.rm=TRUE) )
## [1] 0.2051711
```

Compute the **R-factor** (Abbaspour et al., 2009; Schuol et al., 2008), which represents the average width of the user-defined uncertainty bounds divided by the standard deviation of the observations:

```
( rf <- hydroGOF::rfactor(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, na.rm=TRUE) )
## [1] 0.4123385
```

A good model should bracket most of the measured data (i.e., large P-factor, with a maximum of 1) with the smallest possible R-factor (minimum of 0).

10.4.5 95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU)

The *best* simulated streamflows can now be plotted along with the **95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU)** (Abbaspour et al., 2007, 2009; Schuol et al., 2008):

```
main.uncert <- paste0("Uncertainty bounds SWAT+: ",
                     Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")" )
Qobs.col     <- "black"
best.sim.col <- "blue"
bands.col    <- "lightblue"

Qsim.best.zoo <- zoo(model.best, time(Qobs.zoo.cal) )
```

```

plot(Qobs.zoo.cal, xaxt="n", xlab="", type="n", main=main.uncert, ylab="Q, [m3/s]") # empty plotting ar
drawTimeAxis(Qobs.zoo.cal) # time axis
plotbandsonly(lband=q025, uband=q975) # 95 PPU
lines(Qobs.zoo.cal, col=Qobs.col, lwd=0.3) # Qobs
lines(Qsim.best.zoo, col=best.sim.col, lwd=0.3) # best simulation
grid()

legend("topright", legend=c("Qobs", "best.sim", "95PPU"), lty=c(1, 1, NA),
      pch=c(NA, NA, 15), col=c(Qobs.col, best.sim.col, bands.col),
      bty="n", cex = 1.2)

legend("topleft", legend=c(paste0("P-factor: ", round(pf, 2)),
                          paste0("R-factor: ", round(rf, 2)) ),
      bty="n", cex = 1.2)

```


Figure 26: 95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU) for model simulations during the calibration period.

10.4.6 Uncertainty in flow duration curve

Use the `fdcu` function included in the `hydroTSM` R package to plot the observed flow duration curve (FDC), the FDC of the *best* simulated streamflow, and the flow duration curves for the 2.5 and 97.5 weighted quantiles of model simulations obtained during the calibration period:

```

main.uncert <- paste0("Flow duration curves SWAT+ model: ", Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")")
bands.col <- "lightskyblue1"

par(mfrow=c(3,1))
fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.best.zoo, bands.col=bands.col,
     main=main.uncert, log="") # empty plotting area
grid()
fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.best.zoo, bands.col=bands.col,
     main=main.uncert, log="y") # empty plotting area
grid()
fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.best.zoo, bands.col=bands.col,
     main=main.uncert, log="x") # empty plotting area

```

grid()

Figure 27: Flow duration curve of the observed (black line) and best simulated (blue line) streamflows. In addition, flow duration curves for the 2.5 and 97.5 weighted quantiles of model simulations obtained during the calibration period. The upper panel is the normal flow duration curve, the middle panel has focus on low flows (log='y') and the lower panel has focus on high flows (log='x').

10.4.7 Some comments about P-factor and R-factor

GLUE-like uncertainty analysis (Beven, 2006; Beven et al., 2008; Beven & Binley, 1992) is sensitive to the threshold used to define behavioural parameter sets (`beh.thr`). Lower thresholds usually retain more parameter sets and therefore produce wider posterior ranges for parameters and model simulations (Jin et al., 2010). This can increase the fraction of observations bracketed by the uncertainty band, but it may also reduce the sharpness and practical usefulness of the predictive interval.

In general, decreasing `beh.thr` tends to increase the P-factor, but this improvement is usually obtained at the expense of a larger R-factor. The two indicators should therefore be interpreted together: a high P-factor is desirable only when the associated uncertainty band remains sufficiently narrow for the intended hydrological application.

11 Verification analysis

11.1 Basic analysis of the verification period

Verification is used here to evaluate whether the parameter set obtained during calibration can reproduce an independent period that was not used to guide the optimisation. Because the SWAT+ model was configured to simulate the full period from `Sim.Ini` to `Sim.Fin`, we do not need to rebuild the `TxtInOut` directory or modify the `time.sim` file. Instead, we run the external model with the calibrated parameter set and then subset the simulated and observed streamflow series to the verification window defined by `Ver.Ini` and `Ver.Fin`.

Run SWAT+ with the *best* parameter set obtained during calibration, but compute the goodness-of-fit only over the verification period:

```
hydromod.args <- modifyList(model.FUN.args,
  list(param.values = best.param.cal,
        gof.Ini = Ver.Ini,
        gof.Fin = Ver.Fin
  )
) # 'hydromod.args' END
modeloutput.ver <- do.call(hydromod, hydromod.args)
```

Extract simulated and observed streamflow only for the verification period:

```
Qsim.zoo.ver <- window(modeloutput.ver[["sim"]], start=Ver.Ini, end=Ver.Fin)
Qobs.zoo.ver <- window(Qobs.zoo, start=Ver.Ini, end=Ver.Fin)
```

Graphical comparison between the daily observed and simulated time series obtained with the *best* parameter set for the verification period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, obs=Qobs.zoo.ver, main=main, ylab="Q, [m3/s]", cex=0.3, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 28: Graphical comparison of observed and simulated streamflow time series obtained for the verification period with the best parameter set identified during calibration.

This first visual inspection provides a direct assessment of whether the calibrated parameter set transfers satisfactorily to the independent verification period.

Graphical comparison between **daily** and **monthly** simulated ($Q_{sim.zoo.ver}$) and observed ($Q_{obs.zoo.ver}$) values for the verification period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, obs=Qobs.zoo.ver, ftype="dm",
     FUN=mean, main=main, ylab="Q, [m3/s]", cex=0.4, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 29: Daily and monthly evaluation of simulated streamflows for the verification period using several performance indices.

Graphical comparison between **monthly** and **annual** simulated and observed values for the verification period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, obs=Qobs.zoo.ver, ftype="ma", pt.style="bar",
     FUN=mean, main=main, ylab="Q, [m3/s]", cex=0.4, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 30: Monthly and annual evaluation of simulated streamflows for the verification period using several performance indices.

Graphical comparison between **seasonal** simulated and observed values for the verification period, with one plot for each season:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, obs=Qobs.zoo.ver, ftype="seasonal", ylab="Q, [m3/s]",
     season.names=c("Summer", "Autumn", "Winter", "Spring"),
     FUN=mean, main=main, cex.main=2)
```


Figure 31: Seasonal evaluation of simulated streamflows for the verification period using several performance indices.

Computing the **daily residuals** for the verification period:

```
residuals <- Qsim.zoo.ver - Qobs.zoo.ver  
residuals <- window(residuals, start=Ver.Ini, end=Ver.Fin)
```

Plotting **daily, monthly, and annual** time series, boxplots, and histograms of the **residuals for the verification period**:

```
hydroplot(residuals, FUN=mean, var.unit="m3/s")
```


Figure 32: Analysis of the residuals (simulations - observations) for the verification period at the daily, monthly, and annual temporal scales.

Plot **seasonal** time series and boxplots of the **residuals** for the verification period:

```
hydroplot(residuals, FUN=mean, pfreq="seasonal",
          season.names=c("Summer", "Autumn", "Winter", "Spring"),
          h=0, main=main, cex.main=2)
```


Figure 33: Analysis of the residuals (simulations - observations) for the verification period at the seasonal scale.

11.2 Running behavioural parameter sets

The `verification()` function can be used to run SWAT+ for the behavioural parameter sets retained after calibration. For an external model, the same `hydromod` interface is reused, but the objective-function period is changed from the calibration window to the verification window. This keeps the executable, parameter files, output reader, and observed time series consistent, while ensuring that performance statistics are computed only over the independent verification period.

The variable `verification.drty.out` represents the output directory where the `verification()` function will store the files generated during the verification runs executed for the SWAT+ hydrological model. It is not necessary to create this directory before running the calibration because, if it does not exist, it is automatically created. Keeping all the verification outputs in a dedicated directory makes it easier to inspect parameter sets, objective-function values, model simulations, diagnostic figures, and log files after the calibration has finished.

```
verification.drty.out <- file.path(model.drty, "verification")
```

```
model.FUN.args.ver <- model.FUN.args
model.FUN.args.ver[["gof.Ini"]] <- Ver.Ini
model.FUN.args.ver[["gof.Fin"]] <- Ver.Fin
model.FUN.args.ver[["obs"]] <- Qobs.zoo

out.ver <- verification(fn = "hydromod",
  par = params,
  control = list(drty.out=verification.drty.out,
    gof.name = "KGE2012", # only used for plot titles
    MinMax = "max", # are we looking for a minimum or maximum?
    do.plots = FALSE,
    write2disk = TRUE,
    parallel = "none",
    par.nnodes = 10,
    par.pkgs = c("hydroPSO", "hydroGOF", "hydroTSM", "zoo", "data.table"),
    verbose = TRUE
  ),
  model.FUN = "hydromod",
  model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args.ver
)
```

In the previous code chunk, the argument `par` is a `data.frame` with all parameter sets that will be run with SWAT+. In this case, `params` was already read using the behavioural threshold defined for the calibration analysis. The object `model.FUN.args.ver` keeps the same external-model configuration used during calibration, but updates `gof.Ini` and `gof.Fin` so that the goodness-of-fit value is computed only for the verification period.

11.3 Uncertainty analysis of verification results

11.3.1 Reading all verification results

To proceed with the uncertainty analysis, read all verification results generated by the previous call to the `verification` function:

```
#Reading parameter sets and GoFs
fname.in <- file.path(verification.drty.out, "Verification-ParamValues.txt")
ver <- data.table::fread(file=fname.in, header=TRUE, sep=" ", data.table=FALSE)
params <- ver[, 3:12]
```

```

gofs      <- ver[, "KGE2012"]

fname.in  <- file.path(verification.drty.out, "Verification-ModelOut.txt")
ver       <- data.table::fread(file=fname.in, header=TRUE, sep=" ", data.table=FALSE)

# Removing 'Param' and 'GoF' first two columns
Qsims     <- ver[, -c(1:2)]
model.obs <- window(Qobs.zoo, start=Ver.Ini, end=Ver.Fin)

```

11.3.2 Weighted quantiles of model simulations

Weighted quantiles of model simulations provide an estimate of predictive uncertainty for each model-simulated value, i.e., for each daily streamflow. The weights are based on the goodness-of-fit values obtained during verification for each complete simulated time series.

User-defined weighted quantiles for each model simulation are obtained by combining the ensemble of simulations in `Qsims` with the corresponding goodness-of-fit values in `gofs`.

In this tutorial, the `wquantile` function from `hydroPSO` is used to compute the 2.5, 50, and 97.5 weighted quantiles for each simulated value, by setting `probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975)`:

```

Qsim.025.q50.q975 <- wquantile(Qsims, weights=gofs, byrow=FALSE, probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975),
                               normwt=TRUE, verbose=FALSE)
round( head(Qsim.025.q50.q975), 3)

```

```

FALSE      2.5%   50%  97.5%
FALSE Sim1  8.806 12.390 49.290
FALSE Sim2  8.094 11.460 48.599
FALSE Sim3  6.515 10.620 48.165
FALSE Sim4  6.027  9.897 47.614
FALSE Sim5  5.738  9.261 46.911
FALSE Sim6  5.480  8.659 46.293

```

To plot the uncertainty bounds for each value simulated during the verification period, transform the weighted quantiles 2.5 and 97.5 into zoo objects:

```

dates.ver <- dip(Ver.Ini, Ver.Fin)
q025      <- zoo(Qsim.025.q50.q975[,1], dates.ver)
q975      <- zoo(Qsim.025.q50.q975[,3], dates.ver)

```

11.3.3 P-factor and R-factor

Computing the **P-factor** (Abbaspour et al., 2009; Schuol et al., 2008), which represents the percentage of observations that are within the user-defined uncertainty bounds:

```
( pf <- hydroGOF::pfactor(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, na.rm=TRUE) )  
  
## [1] 0.1695817
```

Computing the **R-factor** (Abbaspour et al., 2009; Schuol et al., 2008), which represents the average width of the user-defined uncertainty bounds divided by the standard deviation of the observations:

```
( rf <- hydroGOF::rfactor(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, na.rm=TRUE) )  
  
## [1] 0.3963158
```

A good model should bracket most of the measured data (i.e., large P-factor, with a maximum of 1) with the smallest possible R-factor (minimum of 0).

11.3.4 95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU)

The *best* simulated streamflows obtained during verification can now be plotted along with the **95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU)** (Abbaspour et al., 2007, 2009; Schuol et al., 2008):

```
main.uncert <- paste0("Uncertainty bounds SWAT+: ",  
                     Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")" )  
Qobs.col <- "black"  
best.sim.col <- "blue"  
bands.col <- "lightblue"  
  
plot(Qobs.zoo.ver, xaxt="n", xlab="", type="n", main=main.uncert, ylab="Q, [m3/s]") # empty plotting a  
drawTimeAxis(Qobs.zoo.ver) # time axis  
plotbandsonly(lband=q025, uband=q975) # 95 PPU  
lines(Qobs.zoo.ver, col=Qobs.col, lwd=0.3) # Qobs  
lines(Qsim.zoo.ver, col=best.sim.col, lwd=0.3) # best simulation during the verificati  
grid()  
  
legend("topright", legend=c("Qobs", "best.sim", "95PPU"), lty=c(1, 1, NA),  
      pch=c(NA, NA, 15), col=c(Qobs.col, best.sim.col, bands.col),  
      bty="n", cex = 1.2)  
  
legend("topleft", legend=c(paste0("P-factor: ", round(pf, 2)),  
                           paste0("R-factor: ", round(rf, 2)) ),  
      bty="n", cex = 1.2)
```


Figure 34: 95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU) for model simulations during the verification period.

11.3.5 Uncertainty in flow duration curve

Use the `fdcu` function included in the `hydroTSM` R package to plot the observed flow duration curve (FDC), the FDC of the *best* simulated streamflow, and the flow duration curves for the 2.5 and 97.5 weighted quantiles of model simulations obtained during the verification period:

```
main.uncert <- paste0("Flow duration curves SWAT+ model: ", Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")")
bands.col <- "lightskyblue1"

par(mfrow=c(3,1))
fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, bands.col=bands.col,
     main=main.uncert, log="") # empty plotting area
grid()
fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, bands.col=bands.col,
     main=main.uncert, log="y") # empty plotting area
grid()
fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, bands.col=bands.col,
     main=main.uncert, log="x") # empty plotting area
grid()
```

Flow duration curves SWAT+ model: Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco (9414001)

Flow duration curves SWAT+ model: Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco (9414001)

Flow duration curves SWAT+ model: Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco (9414001)

Figure 35: Flow duration curve of the observed (black line) and best simulated (blue line) streamflows. In addition, flow duration curves for the 2.5 and 97.5 weighted quantiles of model simulations obtained during the verification period. The upper panel is the normal flow duration curve, the middle panel has focus on low flows (log='y') and the lower panel has focus on high flows (log='x').

12 FAQ

12.1 How can I parallelise my computations?

In `hydroPSO`, parallel execution is controlled through the `parallel` element of the `control` list passed to `hydroPSO`. For external models such as `SWAT+`, this can reduce computing time when the model function is sufficiently expensive or when a large swarm and many iterations are used.

12.2 Why do I get some warnings after the calibration?

Warnings are often related to parameter sets that produce non-finite simulations, poor model performance, or numerical conditions that are outside the meaningful range of the hydrological model. In calibration experiments, some particles may visit regions of the parameter space that are hydrologically implausible even if they remain inside the numerical bounds defined by the user. The relevant point is to inspect whether the optimisation completed successfully and whether the final behavioural parameter sets produce meaningful streamflow simulations.

In the previously described cases, some parameter sets return `NA` when used to run `SWAT+`. You might want to have a look to the `./PSO.out/Particles.txt` and `./PSO.out/Model_out.txt` files, to get the values of the parameter sets and the model outputs, respectively, that returned `NA` values.

If you want to reduce the number of warnings, you might explore to change some of the following `control` arguments: `Xini.type`, `boundary.wall...`

12.3 Why the KGE values shown by `ggof` do not match the one obtained during the optimisation?

The objective function used during optimisation may evaluate a specific period, transformation, or subset of the data, whereas `ggof` may compute its statistics over the time series provided to the plotting function. Small discrepancies can also arise when warm-up periods, missing values, or unit conversions are handled differently. For this reason, the objective-function definition used inside the wrapper function should be considered the reference value for the calibration experiment.

12.4 Why do I get different results every time that I run `hydroPSO` with the same input data?

Particle Swarm Optimisation is a stochastic population-based algorithm. Unless the random-number generator is initialised with a fixed seed before calling `hydroPSO`, different runs may start from different initial swarms and may therefore produce different trajectories through the parameter space. To improve reproducibility, use `set.seed()` before running the calibration and report the main calibration settings, including parameter bounds, swarm size, number of iterations, objective function, and stopping criteria.

13 Software details

This tutorial was built under:

```
## [1] "aarch64-apple-darwin23"  
## [1] "R version 4.6.0 (2026-04-24)"  
## [1] "hydroPS0 0.6.0"  
## [1] "hydroGOF 0.7.0"  
## [1] "hydroTSM 0.8.6"  
## [1] "zoo 1.8.15"
```

14 Version history

-) v0.1: May 31th, 2026

15 References

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16 Appendix A: swat2zoo() function

Function to read SWAT+ outputs (.txt files). It has been formulated to be as flexible as possible, and at least up to SWATplus_rev60.5.4 it is able to adequately read streamflow (channel_sd_morph_day.txt).

```
# File swat2zoo.R
# Part of the hydroPSO R package, https://github.com/hzambran/hydroPSO
# http://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/hydroPSO
# http://www.rforge.net/hydroPSO/
# Copyright 2010-2026 Mauricio Zambrano-Bigiarini, Rodrigo Rojas, Rodrigo Marinao
# Distributed under GPL 2 or later

#####
#                               swat2zoo                               #
#####
# Purpose      : To read the 'channel_sdmorph_day.txt' output file of the SWAT+ #
#              model                                             #
#####
# Output       : A zoo object with the streamflows                #
#####
# Author      : Mauricio Zambrano-Bigiarini                       #
# Started:    : 2010 at JRC Ispra                                 #
# Updates:    : 2025 (Rodrigo Marinao)                            #
#             : 29-May-2026 (MZB and ChatGPT)                     #
#####

swat2zoo <- function(file.name = "channel_sdmorph_day.txt", id,
                    first.date = NULL, last.date = NULL, name.col) {

  # Define the expected SWAT+ output layout.
  # line 1: title/metadata
  # line 2: variable names
  # line 3: units
  # line 4 onward: data

  # Check that the required packages are available.
  if (!requireNamespace("data.table", quietly = TRUE))
    stop("Package 'data.table' is required.")

  if (!requireNamespace("zoo", quietly = TRUE))
    stop("Package 'zoo' is required.")

  # Read and standardise the SWAT+ column names from the header line.
  header.line <- readLines(file.name, n = 2L)[2L]
  cn <- strsplit(trimws(header.line), "\\s+")[1L]
  cn <- make.unique(cn)

  # Identify the positions of the columns required to build the zoo object.
  required.cols <- c("mon", "day", "yr", "gis_id", name.col)
  required.pos <- match(required.cols, cn)

  # Stop early if any required column is absent from the SWAT+ output file.
  if (anyNA(required.pos)) {
    stop(
      "Column(s) not found in file: ",

```

```

    paste(required.cols[is.na(required.pos)], collapse = ", ")
  )
} # IF end

# Read only the required columns using numeric positions because header = FALSE.
df.read <- data.table::fread(input = file.name,
                             skip = 3L,
                             header = FALSE,
                             select = required.pos,
                             showProgress = FALSE
                             )

# Assign the SWAT+ column names to the selected columns.
data.table::setnames(df.read, required.cols)

# Convert imported columns to the types required for filtering and time-series creation.
df.read[, mon := as.integer(mon)]
df.read[, day := as.integer(day)]
df.read[, yr := as.integer(yr)]
df.read[, gis_id := as.character(gis_id)]
df.read[, (name.col) := as.numeric(get(name.col))]

# Select the rows corresponding to the requested SWAT+ spatial unit identifier.
index.id <- df.read[["gis_id"]] %in% as.character(id)

# Stop if the requested identifier is not present in the imported data.
if (!any(index.id))
  stop("No rows found for gis_id/id = ", paste(id, collapse = ", "))

# Extract the requested variable as a numeric vector.
main.out <- df.read[[name.col]][index.id]

# Build the date index from the SWAT+ year, month, and day columns.
dates <- as.Date( paste(df.read[["yr"]][index.id],
                       df.read[["mon"]][index.id],
                       df.read[["day"]][index.id],
                       sep = "-"
                     ),
                 format = "%Y-%m-%d"
               )

# Create the zoo time series using the selected variable and date index.
out.zoo <- zoo::zoo(main.out, dates)

# Optionally trim the zoo object to the requested date window.
if (!is.null(first.date) && !is.null(last.date))
  out.zoo <- window(out.zoo, start = first.date, end = last.date)

# Return the final zoo object.
return(out.zoo)
} # 'swat2zoo' END

```

17 Appendix B: calibration.cal Reference

The `calibration.cal` file included with this tutorial is located in `TxtInOut/calibration.cal`. It contains ten SWAT+ parameters selected for calibration:

```
calibration.cal: written by SWAT+ editor v2.3.1 on 2025-09-28 19:47 for SWAT+ rev.60.5.7
10
cal_parm      chg_typ      chg_val      conds      soil_lyr1   soil_lyr2    yr1          yr2
perco         absval       0.50000     0          0           0            0            0
latq_co       absval       0.83500     0          0           0            0            0
alpha         absval       0.00750     0          0           0            0            0
cn2           abschg       2.00000     0          0           0            0            0
awc           pctchg       155.00000   0          1           6            0            0
k             pctchg       105.00000   0          1           6            0            0
flo_min       absval       5.50000     0          0           0            0            0
revap_min     absval       5.50000     0          0           0            0            0
revap_co      absval       0.11000     0          0           0            0            0
deep_seep     absval       0.05000     0          0           0            0            0
```

Users are, of course, free to define their own calibration parameters according to the objectives and requirements of their optimisation problem.

The `calibration.cal` file supports the three native SWAT+ parameter modification methods:

- **absval**: replaces the existing parameter value with the specified value.
- **abschg**: applies an additive adjustment to the existing parameter value.
- **pctchg**: applies a percentage change to the existing parameter value.

In contrast, `hydroPSO` provides three mechanisms for modifying parameters through the `change.type` and `refValue` arguments:

- **repl**: replacement of the parameter value (the traditional `hydroPSO` approach).
- **add**: additive modification, where the optimised value is added to a user-defined reference value.
- **mult**: multiplicative modification, where the optimised value is multiplied by a user-defined reference value.

It is important to distinguish between the SWAT+ and `hydroPSO` implementations. In SWAT+, the `pctchg` keyword represents a percentage adjustment relative to the current value, whereas the `mult` option in `hydroPSO` performs a true multiplicative scaling of the specified reference value.

To avoid ambiguity, this tutorial uses only the replacement (`repl`) option in `hydroPSO` for all calibrated parameters. During each optimisation iteration, `hydroPSO` writes updated parameter values directly to the `calibration.cal` file. SWAT+ then interprets these values according to the change rule (`absval`, `abschg`, or `pctchg`) assigned to each parameter and applies the corresponding modification internally across the relevant model inputs.

For example, the curve number parameter (`cn2`) is defined with the `abschg` change type and a value of `+2.0`. During calibration, `hydroPSO` updates the value stored in `calibration.cal`, after which SWAT+ applies the additive adjustment internally to the corresponding land-use parameters.

Summary of change types used in the particular example of this tutorial:

Param.	SWAT+ change type	hydroPSO directive	Notes
perco	absval	repl	Direct replacement of the percolation coefficient.
latq_co	absval	repl	Direct replacement of the lateral flow coefficient.
alpha	absval	repl	Direct replacement of the baseflow alpha factor.

Param.	SWAT+ change type	hydroPSO directive	Notes
cn2	abschg	repl	hydroPSO writes the target value; SWAT+ applies the additive adjustment internally.
awc	pctchg	repl	hydroPSO writes the target value; SWAT+ applies the percentage adjustment across soil layers 1–6.
k	pctchg	repl	hydroPSO writes the target value; SWAT+ applies the percentage adjustment across soil layers 1–6.
flo_min	absval	repl	Direct replacement of the return-flow threshold.
revap_min	absval	repl	Direct replacement of the revap threshold depth.
revap_co	absval	repl	Direct replacement of the revap coefficient.
deep_seep	absval	repl	Direct replacement of the deep percolation fraction.

This mapping illustrates that, regardless of whether a parameter is ultimately modified through a direct replacement (**absval**), additive adjustment (**abschg**), or percentage adjustment (**pctchg**) within SWAT+, hydroPSO always updates the value in `calibration.cal` using the replacement (**repl**) strategy. The interpretation and application of the specified change rule are then handled internally by SWAT+.

18 Appendix C: Model executable file for UNIX-Like Systems

This launcher script is intended only for UNIX-like operating systems, including Linux and macOS. Windows users should run `rev60.5.7_64rel_win.exe` directly from the `TxtInOut` directory; the wrapper script described below is not required on that platform.

Before running the model on Linux or macOS, ensure that both the launcher script and the corresponding platform-specific executable have execute permissions. For example:

```
chmod +x rev60.5.7_64rel_unix_like.sh
chmod +x rev60.5.7_64rel_linux
```

or, on macOS:

```
chmod +x rev60.5.7_64rel_unix_like.sh
chmod +x rev60.5.7_64rel_mac
```

At runtime, the launcher automatically detects the operating system and delegates execution to the appropriate binary.

18.1 Platform-Specific Behaviour

18.1.1 Linux

On Linux, the launcher simply executes:

```
./rev60.5.7_64rel_linux
```

The Linux executable can also be run directly because no additional environment variables are required. The wrapper is provided primarily for consistency across supported platforms.

18.1.2 macOS (Darwin)

On macOS, the launcher first sets:

```
export DYLD_LIBRARY_PATH=.
```

before executing:

```
./rev60.5.7_64rel_mac
```

This step ensures that the bundled Intel OpenMP runtime library (`libiomp5.dylib`), located in the same `TxtInOut` directory as the executable, is available to the macOS dynamic loader. Without this configuration, the executable may fail to start due to a missing library dependency.

The OpenMP runtime is required because **SWAT+** was compiled using the Intel Fortran/oneAPI toolchain. Distributing `libiomp5.dylib` alongside the executable eliminates the need for users to install the full Intel runtime environment while preserving support for OpenMP-based parallel execution.

18.1.3 Other Operating Systems

If the launcher is executed on an unsupported platform, it displays a clear message indicating that no compatible executable is available and instructs the user to obtain the appropriate binary for their system.

18.2 Summary

The launcher provides a single entry point for running **SWAT+** across UNIX-like platforms. Although it performs no additional configuration on Linux, it automatically handles the OpenMP runtime dependency required on macOS, ensuring that the correct executable is launched with the appropriate environment settings.

```
#!/bin/bash

SCRIPT_DIR="$(cd "$(dirname "${BASH_SOURCE[0]}")" && pwd)"
cd "$SCRIPT_DIR"

OS_NAME="$(uname -s)"
ARCH_NAME="$(uname -m)"

if [[ "$OS_NAME" == "Linux" ]]; then
    ./rev60.5.7_64rel_linux
elif [[ "$OS_NAME" == "Darwin" && "$ARCH_NAME" == "arm64" ]]; then
    export DYLD_LIBRARY_PATH=.
    ./rev60.5.7_64rel_mac
else
    echo "Unsupported platform ${OS_NAME} ${ARCH_NAME}. Check or compile a matching SWAT+ executable."
    exit 1
fi
```